

x MBA Dissertation Project

Strategic Evaluation and Implementation of

**Information Technology for Sustainable
Competitive Advantage in Hospitality Industry**

x By

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**Business Project Submitted to Kensington College of Business,
University of Wales in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the
degree of Master in Business Administration: Marketing**

K 29/04/2010

H London, United Kingdom

Acknowledgements

Eventhough, at the end this is individual work it could be impossible to be completed without support, inspiration, advice and motivation by others. By using this moment I would like to name people who are the part of this project.

It was my pleasure to work on this project with my advisor Mr.K.Bakht. Dr. Cihan Cobanoglu, my graduate lecturer at Bilkent University, who guided me with my research topic and provided very valuable suggestions. Throughout my entire project this individuals guided me, supported me, advised me, shared their knowledge and encouraged me.

Once we accept our limits, we go beyond them.

I want to thank the hotel managers who accepted my proposal to have interviews with them and contributed by providing valuable information by sharing their experience, knowledge, management strategy and opinions. Those managers are Mr. Grant MacFarlane from Royal Garden Hotel; Mr. Gerard Denny, Mr. Elliot Corbett, Mr. Jawad Sabir from Jumeirah Carlton Tower; Mr. Bogachan Cakin from Ankara HiltonSA. Without their encouragement it would be impossible to understand the reality in hotel industry.

Last, and certainly not least, I would like to thank my family who believed in me, encouraged me and showed patience throughout my entire research period. They are truly a great family and I am blessed with them.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS ii

LIST OF FIGURES AND TABLES vi

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY viii

ABBREVIATIONS xiii

1 INTRODUCTION 1

1.1 AREA OF RESEARCH AND SCOPE 1

1.2 RESEARCH OBJECTIVES 1

1.2.1 STRUCTURE 1

1.4 UNDERSTANDING THE PROBLEM 2

2 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORKS OF IT INVESTMENT 10

2.1 Business Case View 10

2.2 Critical Success Factors (CSFs) Model 11

3 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY 24

3.1 Research Paradigm 24

3.2 Research Approach 25

3.3 Data Sources 25

3.3.1 Secondary Sources 26

3.3.2 Primary Sources 27

3.4 Data Collection 27

4 FACTS AND FINDINGS 34

4.1 Chapter 1 34

4.1.1 Finding 1: Impact of Technology 35

4.1.2 Finding 2: Impact of Business Strategy 36

4.2 Chapter 2 37

4.3 Chapter 3 38

5 ANALYSIS 47

5.1 Understanding the Business Model 47

5.2 Understanding the IT Investment Model 50

5.3 Impact Analysis 51

6 CONCLUSION 55

7 RECOMMENDATIONS 56

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~ Albert Einstein.

Table of Contents

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	II
LIST OF FIGURES AND TABLES	VI
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	VII
ABBREVIATIONS.....	VIII
1 INTRODUCTION.....	1
1.1 AIMS AND OBJECTIVES OF RESEARCH	1
1.2 RESEARCH QUESTION	1
1.3 STRUCTURE	1
1.4 UNIQUENESS OF CONTRIBUTION.....	2
2 LITERATURE REVIEW	3
2.1 EVALUATION OF IT INVESTMENT	3
2.1.1 <i>Measurement Dilemmas</i>	4
2.1.2 <i>IT investment measurement techniques</i>	5
2.1.3 <i>IT effect on profitability, productivity and efficiency</i>	6
2.1.4 <i>Key areas of hotel investment in IT in hospitality</i>	8
2.2 COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE	10
2.2.1 <i>Information and Data Management</i>	11
2.2.2 <i>Sustaining Competitive Advantage</i>	12
2.2.3 <i>Strategic use of IT to enhance decision making</i>	13
2.3 IMPLEMENTATION PROCESS	14
2.3.1 <i>People and systems</i>	15
2.3.2 <i>Organisation structure</i>	16
2.3.3 <i>Resource planning</i>	17
3 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORKS OF IT INVESTMENT	19
3.1 RESOURCE BASE VIEW	19
3.2 DECOMPOSED THEORY OF PLANNED BEHAVIOR.....	21
4 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY.....	24
4.1 RESEARCH PHILOSOPHY.....	24
4.2 RESEARCH APPROACH.....	26
4.3 RESEARCH STRATEGY	28
4.3.1 <i>Secondary Research</i>	30
4.3.2 <i>Qualitative Interviews</i>	30
4.3.3 <i>Data collection</i>	31
4.4 LIMITATIONS	32
5 FACTS AND FINDINGS.....	34
5.1 OBJECTIVE 1.....	34
5.1.1 <i>Tangible Aspect Evaluation Techniques</i>	35
5.1.2 <i>Intangible aspect evaluation methods</i>	35
5.2 OBJECTIVE 2.....	38
5.3 OBJECTIVE 3.....	44
6 ANALYSIS	47
6.1 UNDERSTANDING HOTEL'S INVESTMENT PRIORITIES	47
6.2 STAKEHOLDER'S AFFECT ON DECISION MAKING PROCESS	50
6.3 HUMAN BARRIERS	51
7 CONCLUSION	53
8 RECOMMENDATIONS.....	55

9 REFLECTIONS.....	56
10 BIBLIOGRAPHY.....	57
11 APPENDICES.....	63
11.1 APPENDIX 1 - HOTEL CATEGORY EXPLANATIONS	63
11.2 APPENDIX 2 - INTERVIEWEES.....	64
11.3 APPENDIX 3 - INTERVIEW QUESTIONS	65
11.4 APPENDIX 4 - INTERVIEW MEETING MINUTES.....	66
11.5 APPENDIX 5 - LIST OF COUNTRIES COVERED.....	72

List of Figures and Tables

Figure 1: Resource Based View.....	20
Figure 2: The DTPB.....	22
Figure 3: The research 'onion'.....	25
Figure 4: Methodological assumptions of the main paradigms.....	29
Figure 5: Hotel Characteristic Map.....	32
Figure 6: Stakeholder analysis.....	41

Executive summary

This study analyses the evaluation and implementation processes of Information Technology (IT) investment in the hospitality industry by considering hospitality/hotel industry as a whole. The main purpose of this study is to investigate the factors that affect the IT investment decision making process and understand whether IT investment is considered as a strategically important tool that can add value to business or business demand tool that enables operation to flow.

As hotels face severe competition in the globalised world, the use of technology can create competitive advantage. The managers understanding of technology potential can be affected by organisational structure and culture. The findings are organised according to the research objectives which are as mentioned before:

1. Understanding IT benefits by identifying both intangible and tangible aspects of IT will affect decision making process.
2. Knowledge and skill of stakeholders highly affect implementation of required innovative technology as a result hotel industry is competitively slower in conducting innovative technology than other industries.
3. Staff training and improving staff skills are the main components of the effective implementation and efficient use of IT.

The result shows that hotels in property level use more financial methods than hotels in corporate level. Management skills and educational level has affect on the use of the evaluation methods. Technological efficiency is explained as a distribution of best-practice technology for management activities (Barros, et al., 2009). The efficiency measurement will help hotel management not only analyze the efficient use of technology but to better manage investment and to understand the requirement of technical experts. As the availability of skilled staff decreases hotels will require more training facilities which is evidenced by the results of findings. Moreover, training can be considered as a motivational factor that increase employee's willingness to adopt a new technology.

Abbreviations

ABR – Activity Benefit Realisation	SAM – Social Actor Model
AHLA – American Hotel and Lodging Association	SCM – Supply Chain Management
AHMA – American Hotel and Motel Association	SEM – Structured Equation Modelling
AIT – Advanced Information Technology	SERVQUAL – Service Quality
AST – Adaptive Structuration Theory	SMHO – Small and Medium sized Hospitality Organizations
CEO – Chief Executive Officer	TAM – Technology Acceptance Model
CFO – Chief Financial Officer	TPB – Theory of Planned Behaviour
CIO – Chief Information Officer	TQM – Total Quality Management
COO – Chief Operation officer	TRA – Theory of Reasoned Action
CRS – Central Reservation System	YM – Yield Management
CSLC – Customer Service Life Cycle	
DEA – Data Envelopment Analysis	
DTPB – Decomposed Theory of Planned Behaviour	
F&B – Food and Beverage	
GM – General Manager	
HIS – Hotel Information System	
IDT – Innovation Diffusion Theory	
IRR – Internal Rate of Return	
IT – Information Technology	
ICT – Information and Communication Technology	
MNE – Multinational Enterprises	
NPV – Net Present Value	
PBP – Payback Period	
PMS – Property Management System	
RBV – Resource Based View	
ROI – Return on Investment	

1 Introduction

1.1 Aims and Objectives of Research

The purpose of the research is the strategic evaluation and implementation of IT investment in hospitality industry. The study will be combination of positivistic and phenomenological research methods which are cross-sectional studies and grounded theory. The findings are organised according to the research objectives which are as mentioned before:

1. Understanding IT benefits by identifying both intangible and tangible aspects of IT will affect decision making process.
2. Knowledge and skill of stakeholders highly affect implementation of required innovative technology as a result hotel industry is competitively slower in conducting innovative technology than other industries.
3. Staff training and improving staff skills are the main components of the effective implementation and efficient use of IT.

1.2 Research Question

The main research question is related to define the establishments with the most innovative IT strategy and define the management perspective and purpose of the investments. Moreover, the finding will provide the reasons of investing less in IT by the specified less innovative establishments. As the scholars struggle to identify the tool to evaluate the IT investment profitability, only effective and efficient use of IT by effectively managing the organizational assets will create the difference between successful and less successful organizations. The result of the research will enable to rate the hotel establishments by the innovation rate which is the level of the IT investment and the management strategy.

1.3 Structure

In this study the author investigates the evaluation and implementation process of IT by understanding the background of IT in hotel industry by analysing literature and by including both hotel and other industries. However, as hotel industry is analysed the in-depth literature discussions were followed. As a guide to answer the research objectives the author identified the main frameworks to be used that was followed by the explanation of methodology conducted. After drawing the big picture by identifying the framework and method used the findings

were discussed and analysed to make a conclusion. During the course of the research author reminds the main objectives to the reader in order to ease the reading process and keep the focus on the research objectives.

1.4 Uniqueness of Contribution

The uniqueness of this research is related to the framework used which is Resource Based View (RBV). It was found that RBV model was not commonly used in IT research in hospitality industry as none of the literature covered this framework. The uniqueness of this framework is that it permits the researcher to analyse the IT assets and IT capabilities. This was valued as an important view to analyse IT as it enable the research to recognise the importance of intangibles (Bharadwaj, 2000).

2 Literature Review

The IT requirement should support the organizational strategy as the organization requires a certain technology to gain guest satisfaction and control over the operations. According to McKinsey survey the majority (79%) of CIOs were agreed that their IT strategy is developed by considering the business strategy and IT plans are the reflection of business and IT strategy (McKinsey, 2008). There are no commonly agreed structures to make strategy planning in organizational level and at IT level (Robson, 1997). However, it is crucial to understand the impact of IT objectives upon the organization as it is the part of the organization that provides effective control of the data and information. Controlling data and information means controlling external and internal factors of the organization that is important for the modern management.

The following chapter will critically evaluate the previously completed research on methods related to strategic IT investment. In order to show the relevance of the previously conducted research the author analysed the previous research under the main subject areas which are strategic IT evaluation and implementation process in hospitality industry.

2.1 Evaluation of IT investment

Despite the large amount of IT investments in hospitality industry there are inconsistencies in evaluation methods used to measure the effectiveness and productivity of IT investment. Many studies mentioned that no significant relationship exists between IT investment and the organizational performance which can be associated with the value of information itself (Ham *et al.*, 2005, Karadag *et al.*, 2009). The lack of adequate procedures to monitor the effectiveness of IT investment is another reason that affects the IT investment evaluation process. From the literature review IT investment decisions can be made by focusing on the IT benefits and productivity.

Strategic choice is the element of management that require a basic strategic analysis. For this reason, managers should take into their attention the generation of options, evaluation of options and selection of strategy (Robson, 1997). Certain criteria or 3

factors can affect the final decision of evaluation process. The strategic choice can have financial and non-financial factors which will be closely analysed in the following parts. The strategic choice in general is the feasibility and suitability of IT investment strategy with organizational strategy (Robson, 1997). There can be different strategic choices put on the table and the management will require matching the IT strategy with the organizational strategy. The culture and the power structure of the organization is another factor that will affect the choice. A careful analysis will be required to evaluate the importance of IT for the organizational strategy.

2.1.1 Measurement Dilemmas

Several studies showed that the benefits from IT investment were less than projected which questioned the measurement methods used to evaluate IT investment. There are widespread beliefs that can extract and exploit more value from IT rather than the economic measurement of productivity. In order to understand the IT capability we need to identify what are the components of IT function. IT function can be explained by identifying two components that are intangible (qualitative) and tangible (quantitative) resources. Tangible resources are physical IT infrastructure and technical skills of managers and staff while intangible resources are knowledge assets, customer orientation, and synergy (Bharadwaj, 2000). Organisations create competitive advantage by assembling both tangible and intangible resources that work together but cannot be evaluated separately.

Scholars suggested several methods to specify intangible IT benefits. Pitt *et al.* (1995) suggests service quality (SERVQUAL) measurement by using six categories which are grouped into system quality, information quality, use, user satisfaction, individual impact, and organizational impact. David *et al.* (1996) argues that there is no single measurement or set of measurements of IT productivity and efficiency. The challenges to measure IT productivity in the hotel industry was related with the different attributes of input and output of hotel industry (Flitman, 2003). Those attributes are related to the different tasks undertaken during the project, different cost of labour hours, and a common set of weights applied across all projects. The main motivational factor for IT investment may not always be productivity, but to improve customer service and to create diversified service (David *et al.*, 1996). Indeed, hotel executives believe that technology has had a negative financial impact (David *et al.*, 1996; Cline, 1999).

Managers should understand that the technological investment's payback time is extensive and the intangible aspects of IT investment are difficult to measure.

2.1.2 IT investment measurement techniques

There are two methods to evaluate the IT investment: financial and non-financial methods. The financial evaluation choices will be related to the investment cost and the return from the investment by using financial methods such as Net Present Value (NPV), Internal Rate of Return (IRR), Payback Period (PBP) and Return on Investment (ROI) (Anandarajan and Wen, 1999; Alshawi *et al.*, 2003; Karadag *et al.*, 2009). Some of the methods can show limitation and inconsistency related to the project nature (Pike *et al.*, 2006). For example, PBP is the fastest way of evaluating investment as it tells us the length of time taken for the investment to be repaid against net cash flow (Atrill, 2000). The majority of decision makers (85%) stated that they consider using non-financial techniques rather than financial techniques to make evaluation of IT investment (Suwardy *et al.*, 2003).

Barros *et al.* (2009) demonstrates the use of mathematical programming techniques called Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) to evaluate the efficiency and productivity growth in hotel industry. DEA method has advantage over the other methods as it permits the use of multiple inputs and outputs. However, Flitman (2003) argues that DEA cannot be used as a stand-alone tool to estimate the project efficiency. The limitation of this method was related to the possibility of mismatching the weights of output and input with its value and the varying skills of IT users that affect the efficient use of a technology. On the other hand, Shafer *et al.*, (2000) suggests the use of DEA for evaluating the efficiency and effectiveness of investment in IT as it provides the flexibility to include the relevant inputs and outputs, the information how inefficient input and output can be adjusted, and the opportunity to further analyse the results.

Non-financial techniques are considered as soft benefits (Whitaker, 1987) or intangibles which are hard to measure but the key to make investments decisions (Yousef, 2009). These intangibles factors are best fit to technical requirements, previous contact, new version, instruction and other (Suwardy *et al.*, 2003). Increase in IT expenditure and difficulty to identify the benefits, makes the decision making process more complicated. High IT expenditure doesn't mean the best financial results will be reached. Ross and

Weill (2002) and Carr (2003) provide some quick tips to 5

evaluate IT investment and what to consider when making decisions. However, the unique nature of the hotel products and services make the decision making process more complicated. The main differentiating factor of hotel industry from manufacturing industry is related to product and service demand, perishable nature of products and services, and short cycle of production, delivery and consumption of products and services (Winata and Mia, 2005).

Use of mathematical techniques alone are not enough to understand the true value of IT investment as intangible benefits associated with IT projects should be considered to fully value IT investment. These intangible benefits are strategic benefits that are hard to quantify and criteria that can be easily affected by the different factors (Anandarajan *et al.*, 1999). Anandarajan *et al.*, (1999) give high importance to identify intangible benefits next to the tangible benefits in order to fully understand costs and benefits of IT investment. Fink (2003) identifies key processes associated with IT benefit management by selecting Activity Benefit Realisation (ABR) approach. By using this approach, Fink (2003) ensures operational effectiveness by identifying subsystem costs and benefits.

2.1.3 IT effect on profitability, productivity and efficiency

IT investment resulted in greater productivity, decrease in costs and increase in employee efficiency and revenue (David, 1996; Scott, 1999; Siquaw *et al.*, 2000; Alshawi, 2003; Fink, 2003; Orfila-Sintes *et al.*, 2005; Ham *et al.*, 2005; Chathoth, 2007; Kim, 2008). Shafer (2000) indicates that the profitability will be reached by the improvement in operational efficiency as a result of IT investment. According to Denny (2009) IT investment definitely affects the hotel efficiency in positive way. For example, from an operational perspective advanced technology provides greater operational flexibility, greater knowledge about business, better customer relationship and management facilities (Denny, 2009). However the effective and efficient use of IT can be determined by factors such as lodging segment, lodging type, brand affiliation status and administrative complexity (Main, 1995; Camison, 2000; Sigala, 2001; Daghou, Orfila-Sintes *et al.*, 2005; Karadag *et al.*, 2009) Other factors that affect IT level of use are the country, location and hotel size (Buhalis and Main, 1998; Siquaw *et al.*, 2000; Wei *et al.*, 2001; Buick, 2003; Law and Jogaratham, 2005). Orfila-6

Sintes (2005) identifies the three main characteristics of the hotel industry that can influence IT investment which are hotel category, governance and chain structure. The study result shows that the increase in size of the hotel, chain hotels, and effective human capital skills are the main factors that motivate hotels to invest in IT (Orfila-Sintes, 2005). However, overall hotels are very slow in adopting new technology (Sugaw *et al.*, 2000).

According to the "Hospitality 2000: the technology" survey, hotels spent an average 3.1 percent of revenue on IT investment (Cline, 1999). However, before making any decisions the executives should understand the challenges that can be faced to avoid IT disasters. The main areas of consideration before making the final decision should be the IT spending, IT initiatives, IT infrastructure, IT services, security and privacy risks and commitment on the part of the managers (Ross and Weill, 2002).

Moreover, Ham *et al.*, (2005) examines the effect of IT applications on the performance of four strategic areas in a hotel which are front office, back office, food and beverage department and guest-related applications. It was concluded that there are significant effect of front office, back office and restaurant and banquet management systems on performance. While, guest-related applications had no affect on the performance of hotels. This study was coincident with David *et al.* (1996). However, Chathoth (2007) suggests that hotels need to become more technologically oriented in order to be more efficient to provide quicker responses to the hotel guest's needs and wants.

Barros *et al.* (2009) concludes that technical efficiency is related to both inputs and outputs in the process of production. Connolly (1999) states the importance of exploiting distribution channels to gain market share by increasing the sales while reducing overheads. As the purpose of IT investment can differ from hotel to hotel, the traditional appraisal techniques cannot be enough and as a result the productivity of IT cannot be measured but can be only identified. Survey conducted by Barros *et al.* (2009) notices that the most of the managers implemented the technology knowing that it will not result in the measurable productivity improvement but expected to improve customer service and to offer more augmented services.

In 2008 the IT department rate themselves more effective than the previous year which was evidenced by the 75% increase in efficiency (McKinsey survey, 2008). The reason was related to the increase in importance of IT for the business development as well as decrease in the efficiency in IT that required more attention from the management. McKinsey survey (2008) result shows that 40% of companies will still invest in new technology although the last year's results were showing 69% of companies are planning to invest in IT.

Although, the economic condition affected the investment in IT there is still a high need to decrease the operating expenses. So as the new IT investment will take place the companies are expected to have a decrease in operating expenses. By using IT the organization can decrease unwanted transactions by monitoring the value chain, which will create an opportunity to decrease the cost. As the cost is reduced the power of the buyer can be reduced as the company will have more opportunity to switch the prices. The study conducted by Chathoth (2007) identifies the hospitality areas that involve high transaction costs and provides the suggestions how this transaction cost can be managed by IT applications. The areas that involve transaction costs that can be managed by using IT are (Chathoth, 2007):

- The reservation transaction as it involves agents
- The registration process that involve front desk agents
- Guest services involving departments such as front office, housekeeping, engineering, concierge and food and beverage

The automation of the operation can require less labour force which can reduce the supplier power (Robson, 1997). The improved IT can affect the service quality in hotel which will attract more customer and competitive advantage can be reached by standardizing the service and controlling it by using IT and IS (Hidding, 2001).

2.1.4 Key areas of hotel investment in IT in hospitality

In last decades the hotel industry showed a trend of shifting the organisational structure from property level to chain level (Connolly, 1999) which requires some sophisticated and enhanced technology to connect different hotels in different locations. The head office will have control over the brands by analysing and evaluating each operation of

the different brands and make decision that is significant for that channel only (Sigala *et al.*, 2001). Early studies have shown that the use of technology in hospitality started with the basic accounting system introduction in 1976 (Whitaker, 1987). During 1970s hotel industry used IT to automate reservation system and to set a centralised system (Sigala *et al.* 2001).The data was stored in the computers for reporting and decision making. However, the yield system didn't exist to insure effective management (Sigala *et al.*, 2001). Furthermore, the efficiency of the web applications allowed hotels to connect their system to network so that customers can make online reservations a through central reservation system (CRS).

Despite the technological evolution the implementation process took a very slow start in hospitality and in 1986 there were still establishments using mechanical adding machines (Whitaker, 1987). As technology expanded the hotels spent more on property management systems (PMS) that were followed by yield management (YM), central reservation systems (CRS), sales and catering systems, e-mail/Internet, database marketing, point of sale, food and beverage, guestroom technologies and kiosks for check-in and check-out (Cline, 1999). There are some significant improvements noticed in deploying technology into the sales functions, with overall 70% adoption rate of sales automation (Cline, 1999). It is the indication of the technological importance for the strategic sales decisions.

More studies on hotel industry addressed the degree of using IT application such as Total Quality Management (TQM), CRM and supply chain management (SCM) to enhance service quality, operational efficiency and increase overall performance (Alshawi *et al.*, 2003; Daghous and Barkhi, 2009). Moreover, as research by Winata and Mia (2005) attest, the importance of effective use of information and communication technology (ICT) to make budgetary decision between hotel departments, Sahadev and Islam (2005) analysed the factors that influence the information communication technology adoption propensity in the hotel industry. Those factors are:

- (1)The percentage of consumers who visit the hotel's location from high internet penetration countries;
- (2)The overall market size of the hotel's location;
- (3)The level of competition between the firms in the locality;

- (4) The size of the hotel;
- (5) The scope of activities of the hotel;
- (6) The grade/type of the hotel; and
- (7) The age of the hotel.

2.2 Competitive Advantage

There is gap between the current priority of the IT and the ideal priority of the IT. The main priority of IT should be focusing on growth of the business rather than making most of affords on reducing IT costs and ensuring compliance with regulations (Macfarlane, 2009). According to Suwardy *et al.* (2003) there are five main reasons why firms invest in IT:

- To increase operating efficiency
- To provide better information to management
- To reduce cost
- To obtain competitive advantage
- To meet customer expectations.

The result shows us that not all IT investment priority is the intention to create competitive advantage but to enhance the operational. On the other hand, the McKinsey survey conducted in 2008 identifies the areas of IT investment impact which are to manage sales and pricing, optimize sourcing and production, enhance support processes, optimize overhead and performance management (McKinsey, 2008). Moreover, there are areas where IT can create significant difference which not affectively delivered by IT. These areas of improvement are to develop new, technology-enabled capabilities, and engagement with business leaders on new ideas/enhancements to existing processes and systems (McKinsey survey, 2008).

Orfila-Sintes *et al.* (2005) mention the changes in the key areas of investment where technology can be transformed into competitive advantage. Those key areas where technology took place are guest rooms, restaurant, kitchen, and hardware and computer system. Cline (1999) states the importance of guest room technologies that will and can provide competitive advantage. The research conducted by Orfila-Sintes *et al.* (2005) also concludes the investment in guest room is very high because tangible assets can 10

the organisation by training and informing other executives (MacFarlane, 2009). Chathoth (2007) develops a conceptual framework regarding the benefits of IT to create customer satisfaction which is the key for sustainable customer loyalty. Piccoli *et al.* (2001) outlines the Customer Service Life Cycle (CSLC) framework for affective and creative use of internet and worldwide web to obtain outstanding customer service. The expansion of business in the global arena creates global competitive environment rather than of country or location related. If greater customer service and better work productivity was reached then e-commerce becomes "the core of the day-to-day" business (Kaplan, *et al.* 2008). Intensified competition requires hotels to explore changes in business and technology (Daghfous and Barkhi, 2009) that can be examined by using eight imperatives for IT organizations which are (Rockhardt *et al.*, 1996):

- 1) Achieve two-way strategic alignment
- 2) Develop effective relationships with line management
- 3) Deliver and implement new systems
- 4) Build and manage infrastructure
- 5) Re-skill the IT organization
- 6) Manage vendor partnerships
- 7) Build high performance
- 8) Redesign and manage the federal IT organization

2.2.2 Sustaining Competitive Advantage

One of the main reasons organizations invest in IT is to obtain competitive advantage. Competitiveness is somehow non-quantifiable and uncertain (Ross *et al.*, 1996). Carr (2003) mentions the narrow focus on technology as a source of competitive advantage is misleading and misguided. Focus on IT-dependent strategy doesn't follow "one-time" decisions, but it consists of interrelated and interlocking activities (Rivkin, 2000). A firm should continually seek for the innovation around its core business strategy that can be successfully carried by the implementation of IT strategy and linking corporate strategy to the IT strategy (Suwardy *et al.*, 2000) If companies can strategically use IT with its all potentials they can finally reach a sustainable competitive advantage (Suwardy *et al.*, 2000; Wade and Hulland, 2004; Piccoli and Ives, 2005).

But the next question arises is "how long can an advantage be sustained?" Hidding (2001) identifies the factors that will affect the length of sustainability by considering the cycle speed of the ecology in which the firms compete. In contrast

(2000) argues that as competing firms have different endowments of IT resources IT infrastructure development times can be estimated from five to seven years. Moreover, the management skills and IT staff skill as a human asset can create better positioning for some firms than their rivals (Bharadwaj, 2000).

According to Robson (1997) rivalry among the existing competitors are greater when the industry is maturing or declining. The implementation of new technology can reduce the rivalry among competitors by offering the improved and advanced technological services. Another way to understand the capability of organization to obtain competitive advantage is to analyse the different stages of IT strategy (Craig *et al.*, 2007). There are some stages that the organization should take and consider in order to use IT as a competitive weapon, which is reached when the IT planning horizon and focus of IT strategy is high on the right corner of the matrix.

On the other hand, van Hoof *et al.* (1996) provides the framework of IS capability by describing the nine core components, which are:

- Leadership
- Business system thinking
- Relationship building
- Making technology work
- Informed Buying
- Contract facilitation
- Contract monitoring
- Vendor development

More importantly van Hoff *et al.* (1996) concentrated on the project management by discussing issues such as technical skills, business skills, interpersonal skills, time horizon and motivating values.

2.2.3 Strategic use of IT to enhance decision making

The decision making process widely involves technological efficiency. The main departments in hotel that use technological advancement to make decisions are the reservation department, sales, finance and front office. Early research showed that only 37% of small and medium sized hospitality organizations (SMHOs) use IT for the

strategic decision making (Main, 1995). Jones (1997) provides the framework to understand the use of IT in reservation decision making. The two main systems of reservation process are Decision making system and Decision support system. The core areas in decision support system are demand analysis and reservations because those areas affect strategic decision making and operational decision making processes. On the other hand, the external environment will have same effect on both systems which shows how competitors and economic environment will influence the decision making process.

This challenge led to practice called yield management (YM). Yield management is all about managing the price with regards to demand in order to reach the maximum profit. The core strategy of any hotel will be to increase profit by reaching the best available price that guests can afford. There are some industry characteristics that lead the YM systems so significantly. Those characteristics are the perishable future of the rooms, fixed capacity, an uncertainty in demand, different market segments with different lead time, and the flexibility of the hotel to change prices (Lewis *et al.*, 2000). By using YM system hotels will benefit from demand forecasting, segments forecasting, better inventory management and better customer relations (Lewis *et al.*, 2000). The inventory management as well as Food and Beverage (F&B) management will use the information obtained from forecasting and make decisions accordingly.

The accurate use of data for decision making will enhance the revenue up to 8% (Jones, 2000). Technology enabled different systems to connect to each other. For example, whenever reservation department make changes on price Front Office department will be able to see those changes without picking up any phone. The study conducted by Camison (2000) focuses on the management of systems by IT usage and impact on administrative and organizational process. In this case IT is seen by hotels as a tool for the "management of human resources" and as "an element of added value within the business strategy" (Camison, 2000).

2.3 Implementation process

The biggest resistance against IT change can come from the organizational culture, structure and management style, and shareholders interest. The research conducted by Karadag *et al.* (2009) states that the methods used by hotels to implement new 14

technology can differ whether the hotel is managed at the property level or corporate level. The result shows that at the corporate level the decisions are made by considering the company strategy while in the property level this decision making method can be ignored. However, the property level hotels can implement a new system easier than the corporate level hotels where the IT is centralised.

Pine's (1992) research determines the factors for the successful transfer of technology in the hotel industry. It identifies "the receiver's ability and willingness to adopt and adapt the particular technology" is the most important factor (Pine, 1992). Van Hoof *et al.* (1996) researched the hotel manager's perception toward computer technology and their opinions about the needs, competency and levels of automation. To improve the ability and to support the willingness toward a new technological transfer, hotels should conduct some level of formal and informal training. However, previous study by Pine (1992) identify the factors that affect the ability of employees to implement new technology which are the ability of education and training on a national basis, the hotel size, type of the hotel and ownership status. The study compares multinational enterprises (MNEs) in developed, newly industrialized and industrialized countries. The study is important as it identifies the different technology transfer level by country type as the successful technological transfer is highly dependent on the receivers' capability and willingness to participate in the transfer process.

IT investment not only consists of the incorporation or modification of technology but also implementation and organizational change to develop and train staff for efficient use of technology. The early study of Whitaker (1987) lists the three organizational barriers which are IT resistance barriers of will, finance, and ability. Efficient use of IT will lead to decrease in errors, decrease in time spent to provide a service and the better customer interaction that will increase the potential of repeated business and increase in revenue (David *et al.*, 1996; Chathoth, 2007).

2.3.1 People and systems

The use of IT in the hospitality industry is associated with the dynamic relationships between stakeholders and other variables that characterize the hotel industry. Empirical research shows that small (less than 100 rooms) and medium-scaled (100-300 rooms) hospitality organizations (SMHO) are reluctant to use IT for the strategic management 15

decision making (Main 1995, Buhalis *et al.* 1998, Siquaw 2000, Wei *et al.* 2001, Orfila-Sintes *et al.* 2005, Daghfous *et al.* 2009). The main reasons for lack of use of IT in SMHO are (Main, 1995):

- Lack of economy of scale
- Age, gender, family and educational level of management
- Lack of training
- Lack of independent advice from suppliers

Considering these reasons stakeholder analysis is important to identify the main players that determine the adaptation and implementation of IT (Whitaker, 1987; Pine, 1992; Buhalis, 1998; Ross and Weill, 2002). To understand the organizational capability to implement IT is important as much as understanding the benefits of IT. Empirical research has indicated that the organization would not fully benefit from IT if barriers of human factors are overlooked (Pine, 1992; van Hoof *et al.*, 1996; Ross and Weill, 2002). Van Hoof *et al.* (1996) identified three main barriers of successful use and implementation of IT, which are:

- A lack of proper training
- High turnover rates
- Limited financial resources

2.3.3 Organisation structure

In order to understand the institutional structure in IT development Rowland (2009) suggests the social actor model (SAM) by focusing on a human act with IT in a social setting. According to SAM organizational members seek to communicate in legitimate ways, the information in an acceptable and standardized format decreases the network conflict and makes the task more actionable and the tailoring of different projects by using professional knowledge will enable completion of the task in hand (Rowlands, 2009). Technology acceptance model (TAM) is another model that explains the use of technology on an individual level (Lam *et al.*, 2007; Kim *et al.*, 2008). TAM describes the technology acceptance or use by behaviour intentions which are affected by attitude toward use, perceived ease of use, perceived value and perceived usefulness.

Another approach to study the role of IT in organizational change is Adaptive Structuration Theory (AST) that focuses on the affect of IT on organizational structure 16

and the human action that affects the IT structure (DeSanctis and Poole, 1994). Affect of IT on organizational structure was defined as a "soft" determinism by Orlikowski (1992), as IT functions consist of intangible attributes. The organizational dimensions that are affected by IT as an external force are structure, size, performance and centralization/decentralization (Orlikowski, 1992). Ross and Weill (2002) state the importance of balancing the capability of organization and IT, no matter whether its operation is centralized or decentralized. The major sources of structure is advanced information technology (AIT) that can be explained as a social structure that is described in two ways: the structural features of the given technology and the spirit of this feature set (DeSanctis and Poole, 1994). Bajgoric and Moon (2009) identifies the main issues in system integration which are the organizational problem and technical problem. The four main disconnection issues that are caused by organizational problems are: disconnection between organizational systems and its IS (Sirvan, 2009), lack of integration aspects of information management into organizational management, disconnection between IT professionals and managers and disconnection between managers and computers (Bajgoric and Moon, 2009). Very little literature mentions the impact of knowledge transfer from one hotel to competitor hotel by individuals that create knowledge spill over (Jacob and Groizard, 2007). It can be related to the tacit and hard to codify nature of information. Knowledge management is the social process that is hard to manage but if managed can create competitive advantage that is hard to imitate by competitors.

2.3.3 Resource planning

Piccoli (2008) provides framework to achieve competitive advantage by identifying the drivers of response lag. Response lag drivers are the characteristic of IT assets that makes the IT-dependent strategic initiative more difficult and costly to imitate by rivals (Piccoli and Ives, 2005). Survey conducted by Craig *et al.*, (2008) finds that 46% of firms agree that they are considering the capability of competitors when deploying IT and 34% agree that they introduce better technology than their competitors. However, competitive advantage reached by deploying better IT can be sustained by identifying four barriers to erosion of competitive advantage which are (Piccoli, 2008):

1. IT-resources barrier
2. Complementary resource barrier
3. IT-project barrier

4. Pre-emption barrier

On the other hand, "Strategic Choice" Model (SCM) is used to describe technology as an internal object (Orlikowski, 1992). The model identifies technology as "a product of ongoing human action, design, and appropriation" (Orlikowski, 1992). According to this model the capability of human agents play a crucial role. Bhattacharjee (1998) identifies the key organizational factors that facilitates or impedes the IT adoption and implementation which are:

- Technological vision
- Process of cost justification
- Support from senior managers
- Ability of corporate reorganization
- "Support network" between employees
- Accuracy of information content
- User involvement and ownership

Ashewi *et al.*, (2003) identify the similar factors that impede the IT implementation process which are a lack of managerial support and failure to identify the full cost implications. In order to avoid these issues it is vital to understand and capture these organizational problems prior to adoption and create the intention to adopt rather than intention to use (Sirvan, 2009). For this reason Karahanna *et al.*, (1999) combined Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) and Innovation Diffusion Theory (IDT) to describe how the attitude toward the adoption of new technology is formed and what will be the final decision of end-user.

On the other hand, Lam *et al.* (2007) developed a new model by combining TAM and TRA that included perceived belief of use and task-technology fit. The result of testing the model showed that perceived IT beliefs had the greatest impact on attitude of hotel employees while task-technology fit was negatively related to attitude.

3 Theoretical Frameworks of IT Investment

This chapter explains the theoretical frameworks that are used to develop a link between IT capability and competitive advantage. In order to achieve to create a competitive advantage we need to identify the capability of the organisation by analysing the resources. Furthermore, the implementation process will be analysed by using frameworks to identify human factors that affect the implementation process.

The criteria used to choose the following models were:

- 1 - Identifies the connection between organisation capability and resources
- 2 - Identifies the key players in decision making process
- 3 - Identifies main factors that negatively influence IT evaluation
- 4 - Identifies main factors that negatively influence IT implementation

The author found it more effective to use these frameworks by combining them together as one framework makes in depth analysis of another framework. The three main theoretical frameworks that were found useful were Resource Based View (RBV), Decomposed Theory of Planned Behaviour (DTPB) and Stakeholder analysis.

3.1 Resource Base View

One of the main reasons organizations invest in IT is to obtain competitive advantage. Competitiveness is somehow non-quantifiable and uncertain (Ross et al., 1996). In order to use IT as a tool for competitive advantage the researcher needs to study the organization's ability to deploy IT to meet strategic objectives. The strategic impact of IT on organizational performance can be examined by conducting a resource-based view (RBV) framework. RBV is the practical tool to understand the role of IT within the firm by exploring and identifying resources that play or can strategically play an important position to create and sustain competitive advantage (Wade and Hulland, 2004). The main idea of the framework is to show how organizational resources are assembled together in order to create competitive advantage (Bharadwaj, 2000). For this reason the main research areas of each literature were analysed under technical and behavioral (managerial) aspects.

Resource Based View (RBV) to recognise the intangible benefits such as customer orientation and organisational knowledge (Bharadwaj, 2000; Rivkin, 2000; Wade and

Hulland, 2004). RBV identifies the organizational resources that can be combined together to create organizational capability toward the sustainable competitive advantage (Bharadwaj, 2000).

Figure 1: Resource Based View

Source: Piccoli and Ives (2005)

The framework is analysed under two main assets which are IT assets and IT capabilities (Piccoli & Ives, 2005). IT assets were examined by two principals which are IT infrastructure and Information Repositories (see Figure 1). In addition, IT capabilities were examined by three principals which are technical skills, management skill and relationship asset. Table 1 shows the research areas of each literature under these principals. It can be noticed from the previous researches that none of the hospitality industry related literatures fully cover the IT capability by analysing under RBV. As a result this research is unique in this field by using RBV framework that is especially important in case of hospitality industry. By using this framework the author will be able to identify intangible resources such as organisational knowledge that is significant to understand IT evaluation process.

Table 1: IT research in hospitality industry

	Authors	IT assets		IT capabilities		
		Infrastructure	IT repositories	Employee skills	Management skills	Relationship assets
1	Whitaker (1987)	X		X		X
2	Pine (1992)			X		X
3	Main (1995)			X	X	
4	van Hoof et al. (1996)	X	X		X	
5	David et al. (1996)	X	X			
6	Buhals & Main (1998)		X	X	X	X
7	Cline (1999)	X	X			
8	Camison (2000)	X				
9	Siquaw (2000)	X				
10	Wei et al. (2001)	X	X		X	
11	Buick (2003)	X				
12	Orfila-Sintes (2005)					X
13	Winata & Mia (2005)				X	
14	Law & Jogaratnam (2005)	X	X	X		
15	Sahadev & Islam (2005)	X				
16	Hann et al. (2005)	X				
17	Jacob & Groizard (2007)			X		
18	Chathoth (2007)				X	X
19	Lam et al. (2007)			X		
20	Kim et al. (2008)		X			
21	Barros et al. (2009)	X				
22	Karadag et al. (2009)		X			
23	Daghous & Barkhi (2009)	X		X	X	X
24	Huh et al. (2009)			X		

3.2 Decomposed Theory of Planned Behavior

The behavioral intention of employees is the essential factor that should be analysed in order to understand a human related barriers of technological transfer. Decomposed theory of planned behavior (DTPB) is the framework that explains the employee's behavioural intention to use innovation technology better than the other frameworks which are Technology acceptance model (TAM) and Theory of planned behavior (TPB).

A study conducted by Huh *et al.* (2009) compared Decomposed Theory of Planned Behaviour (DTPB) and Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) models with TAM concluded that the use of different models depends on the purpose of research. DTPB is the better model to explain employees' behavioural intention to use hotel information system (HIS), predicted attitude toward use, user-friendly HIS design and information integration efforts. While, TAM is considered a better model to assess an individual's attitude regarding WAP services and explain the employees' HIS acceptance decisions.

This framework will be combined with RBV framework's employee skill part as hotel industry is labour intensive industry where the influence of the staff training level should be explained in more details by understanding the reasons behind the behavioural intentions.

Figure 2: The DTPB

Source: Huh *et al.* (2009)

DTPB considers three dimensions of behavioral intention to use: attitude toward use; subjective norms; and perceived behavioral control (see Figure 2). Attitude toward use is explained by perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness and compatibility. Subjective norms are explained by analysing the affect of peer's influence and superior's influence. Finally, perceived behavioral control is analysed under self-efficacy and technical support.

Another framework that was combined with RBV is the stakeholder analysis to show the power level and interest level of each stakeholders that influence evaluation and implementation process of IT investment. The main unique point in stakeholder

analysis was the owner's and government influence that needed to be analysed in depth to understand their level of power under different economic status of country (developing, newly industrialised and industrialised) and different hotel management levels (property and corporate levels).

4 Research methodology

The research methodology is the process that concerns the planning and then deciding a method that is appropriate to answer a research question. The following chapter explains research philosophy, research approach and research strategy to discuss appropriate methods used to answer a research question.

4.1 Research Philosophy

The methodology starts with the understanding of the important assumptions of the research which is the research philosophy. According to Saunders et al. (2007), research philosophy answers the question: "In what extent will the researcher develop the new knowledge that should result in the contribution to literature?"

After reading and analysing the literature the author developed a specific hypothesis to investigate and develop to contribute to literature. As a result the potential relationship between hotel IT investment and hotel characteristics were questioned. The hypothesis arrived at: The effective and efficient use of IT will create sustainable competitive advantage in hotel industry.

The objectives that need to be investigated are:

1. Understanding IT benefits by identifying both intangible and tangible aspects of IT will affect decision making process.
2. IT investment in hospitality industry is related to the hotel characteristics and a level of management knowledge.
3. Staff training and improving staff skills are the main components of the effective and efficient use of IT especially in hotel industry.

Figure 3: The research 'onion'

Source: Saunders et al. (2007)

As seen from the research 'onion' the research philosophy analyses the ways of thinking under epistemology, ontology, axiology and four paradigms (see Figure 3). Epistemology is the philosophical assumptions in which reality is understood as subjectivism (Eriksson & Kovalainen, 2008). Two divisions of ontology are objectivism (social world exists independently of people and their actions) and subjectivism (reality is output of cognitive process) (Eriksson & Kovalainen, 2008). Axiology is a philosophy where an own value of a researcher plays an important role throughout the research process. On the other hand, paradigm can have different explanations in different books. For example, Saunders et al. (2007) explains paradigm as "a way of examining social phenomena". On the other hand, Collis and Hussey (2003) explain it as "a process of scientific practice based on people's philosophies and assumptions about the world and the nature of knowledge". However, the paradigm term was first used by Kuhn (1970), who explained it as a 'normal science' that share two characteristics of achievements which are sufficiently unprecedented achievement and sufficiently open-ended achievement. As the definition of paradigm is hard to achieve its use is widespread in social science (Bryman and Bell, 2007).

According to the purpose of the study the epistemology paradigm was identified as the most appropriate philosophy to be followed. Epistemology constitutes of positivism, realism and interpretivism. The positivism approach explains the research study by associating reality to the nature of the business world. However, the main requirement of the positivism is to produce facts about the research area by observation and measurement of scientific endeavour (Eriksson and Kovalainen, 2008). For this reason as the secondary resources were used to make analysis positivism doesn't exactly fit into this research.

Business world included in this research consists of the social world that is affected by the senses which gives us the idea of reality. As realism considers the affect of senses the philosophy of the research will be to consider the affect of the social world. In this sense realism paradigm explains the research study better than positivism.

The third philosophical position of epistemology is interpretivism. Interpretivism concerns the importance of human role rather than objects (computer and machines) (Saunders et al., 2007). Eventhough, the research is about technology the main objective is to understand the human effect of decision making process and implementation rather than the features of technology used. Interpretivism is another best philosophical explanation of this study as the nature of hotel industry is linked to its labour-intensive component of the industry.

4.2 Research Approach

The research approach is about how the theory is used in the research. There are two main methods that can be named for research approach which are quantitative and qualitative methods (Blumberg, 2008). However, before looking into a deeper analysis of those methods we need to identify and distinguish research study between inductive and deductive studies (Saunders et al., 2007).

The majority of the previous studies in IT investment research have used the inductive approach by identifying the theories and using those theories to analyse the IT investment. In this research, the researcher primarily made use of the inductive method, where less structured approach was taken in order to understand the context of the research. However, during the course of the literature the researcher found the lack of

model to make the precise conclusion. Theoretical frameworks were tested and combined in some parts of the research to analyse the research question in depth. At this point the research method conducted can be explained under multiple methods by underlining the main differences between inductive and deductive methods (see Table 2). The difference between these two methods create the requirement to use both methods simultaneously by generating data inductively and analysing by using an appropriate theoretical frameworks.

Table 2: Major differences between deductive and inductive approaches to research

<i>Deductive emphasises</i>	<i>Inductive emphasises</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific principle • Moving from theory to data • The need to explain causal relationships between variables • The collection of quantitative data • The application of controls to ensure validity of data • The operationalisation of concepts to ensure clarity of definition • A highly structured approach • Researcher independence of what is being researched • The necessity to select samples of sufficient size in order to generalise conclusions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gaining an understanding of the meanings humans attach to events • A close understanding of the research context • The collection of qualitative data • A more flexible structure to permit changes of research emphasis as the research progresses • A realization that the researcher is part of the research process • Less concern with the need to generalize

Source: Saunders et al. (2007)

Qualitative and quantitative methods may come to different conclusions so it is hard to make choice which one is the best method for the current research. Eriksson and Kovalainen (2008) suggest the qualitative method for the business research as it considers "the social world of business and its core processes". On the other hand, quantitative research provides the numeric definition of the research area that will provide the information that is easy to compare (Blumberg, 2008). In short the data in qualitative research comes in the form of words while the data in quantitative research comes in the form of numbers.

The complexity of the research method used is the reality of any research. In order to decide on the quantitative and qualitative methods the researcher analysed the

relationship between inductive and deductive methods with quantitative and qualitative methods. The difference between qualitative and quantitative methods were compared (see Table 3).

Table 3: Comparison of qualitative and quantitative methods

<i>Qualitative research</i>	<i>Quantitative research</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A variety of different theories • Deals with the social and cultural construction of its own 'variables' • Interpretation and understanding • Sensitivity to the context aiming at a holistic understanding of issues studied • Cannot be translated into numbers • Requires more justification 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explanation, testing of hypothesis, and statistical analysis • More prone to structure, standardized, and abstracted modes of collecting and analysing empirical data • Provides more rigorous results

Source: Eriksson and Kovalainen (2008)

The result of the analysis shows that the qualitative method is better suited for an inductive study which is at the same time supporting the research philosophy which is positivism.

4.3 Research Strategy

As the purpose of the research is the strategic use of technology investment the study will be a combination of positivistic and phenomenological research methods which are cross-sectional studies and grounded theory (see Figure 4). Cross-sectional studies involve gathering information from different organizations and groups at the same time in order to analyse how factors can differ from one context to another (Collis and Hussey, 2003).

Figure 4: Methodological assumptions of the main paradigms

Source: Collis & Hussey (2003)

As the results of the literature used were compared to find the similarities and differences the cross-sectional study describes the method used for this research. On the other hand, grounded theory is one example of the inductive approach that allows the researcher to "explore a wide range of business and management issues" (Saunders et al., 2007). Grounded theory is the same as time inductive approach that develop theoretical explanations from the data gathered (Eriksson & Kovalainen, 2008). In this research grounded theory is used to explain and analyse the research result by combining different theoretical frameworks which describes the inductive approach.

The previous researches in this field mainly used the semi-structured questionnaires and interview with the managers of the selected hotels. The result of the previous researches provided information to analyse and identify the main factors that affected the IT investment strategy. An explanatory case study technique was chosen by using the existing theory and research results to elucidate the strategic IT investment in hospitality industry (Collis & Hussey, 2003). The research will cover the hotels in different countries and in different categories. The limitation of the previous studies was considered and analysed to choose this method of research. Although the previous researches covered a broad population of hotel establishments, the findings provided over-generalized conclusions before identifying the factors that were affecting the IT investment in hotel industry.

4.3.1 Secondary Research

As the main research question concerned IT investment in hospitality industry as a whole the data collected should be covering the industry as a whole but the data that is collected from the one part of the country or from a certain characteristic of hotel is not enough to explain the main point. Among the previous researches the largest amount of data collected was from 71 countries (Pine, 1992) that followed by 53 countries (Wei et al., 2001). Moreover, the previous researches separately covers all the areas of IT investment in hotel industry.

According to the method used this business project can be addressed as a literature-based project (Jankowicz, 2005) as instead of imperial data the conceptual argument is presented to sustain the necessary information from the relevant articles that are previously published. Literature-based project does not necessarily mean the summary of the previous researches but more comprehensive evaluation of the previously published articles in order to assemble data to make "a fresh interpretation of what has been written" (Jankowicz, 2005).

The final stage of analysis was backed up by the one-to-one interview with IT managers, IT assistant manager and Hotel manager in different hotel categories to gain more precise information regarding the IT related issues that were identified during the analysis.

4.3.2 Qualitative Interviews

The qualitative interview was conducted in order to produce empirical information for the research question. The interviews were conducted as a face to face interviews and email interviews. Most of the interviews were conducted between the interviewer and the interviewee except one that was made between two interviewees and the interviewer.

The majority of interviewees had a managerial level IT background whose titles are IT managers and IT assistant manager (see Appendix 2). The other interviewees were Hotel manager and Front Office attendant. The main objective was to gather in-depth

information about IT strategy in hotels and gain additional information about hotel strategy and IT user opinion.

The questions asked were prepared in advance according to the role of the person under question. The main focus of the questions was to identify the strategic use of IT in hotels. The questions were carefully tested to make sure that the respondent will provide not direct answer but more explanations. The main issue with the qualitative interview is the difficulty to analyse them (Eriksson and Kovalainen, 2008). For this reason the questions asked were more than prepared questions as some additional questions were asked to clarify the answer. Out of three types of interviews, guided and semi-structured interview type was selected as most of the prepared questions (see Appendix 3) were 'what' and 'how' questions that were under systematic order. In order not to miss out details the researcher used a voice recorder. In all interviews the interviewer asked permission from the interviewees to use a voice recorder to make sure the interviewees are comfortable with a recording. The interview meeting minutes are added in Appendices (see Appendix 4).

4.3.3 Data collection

The secondary data was obtained from 24 academic articles that analysed management of IT in hospitality industry. The data used covers in total 7376 properties in 71 countries that was categorised under developing, industrialised and newly industrialised country. The administrative complexity was managed by analysing the sources by using size category as the hotel investment decision can not only be affected by the brand, segments or location but also the size. In the primary data resource the respondents categorised their hotel types by selecting the choice of categories such as full-service, limited-service, economy, budget, casino, conference, resort etc. (van Hoof, et al., 1996; Siquaw, et al., 2000; Wei, et al., 2001; Kim, et al., 2005; Huh, et al., 2009).

Various research methodologies were compared to identify the factors that were affecting IT investment decision making process. Author analysed hotel industry by seven hotel characteristics which are required to make precise analyses. Those hotel characteristics are hotel size, class, segment, brand, geographical location and country category. Author considered these characteristics after analysing previously conducted

researches. All these characteristics should be considered jointly in order to come up with the best possible solutions. The details of the each category were demonstrated by using Mind-map software (see Figure 5) and the explanation of each category can be found in appendix 1.

Figure 5: Hotel Characteristic Map

Analysing data by hotel characteristics were important in order to avoid the pitfalls of the previous researches. The main pitfalls or limitations that was identified were related to the generalization by only considering hotels in one location, in one country, by one size or avoiding the size effect, avoiding the administration complexity, or incapable of identifying the class/category. For example: Wei et al. (2001) surveyed hotels in 53 countries which cover a broad sample size without concerning the affect of country, region and organizational structure. Understanding the true motivation of IT investment by analysing these seven characteristics that covers all aspects of the hospitality industry will provide valuable information to hotel managers and IT professionals.

4.4 Limitations

The limitation of this research is related to the limitation of the chosen methods, the interviewee's answers and the analysis of the results. In order to

each research methodology the author chose to combine different methods and have a flexible approach toward the use of theoretical frameworks by combining the frameworks. However, cross-sectional studies such as this may not fully capture the complexity of the IT implementation and evaluation process. Consequently, the result of this research can be seen to some extent a limited evidence of the whole IT investment process. Therefore, the result should be taken carefully before making generalisation.

Another limitation is the interviewee's responses to the questions. Although all participants were considered as professionals in their fields it is possible that they have not enough experience in IT investment and IT evaluation process. Another difficulty regarding the interview was a different way of answering the same question which is a reflection of the participant's experience and the interpretation of the question.

Reliability of the data is related to the reliability of the secondary data used. The main limitation that was identified regarding the secondary data was the respondents of the questionnaire were coming from mainly managerial or supervisory levels. For better understanding of the IT implementation process the questionnaires/surveys can be conducted from staff in different departments because managers and supervisors can provide biased views.

The analysis of data can result in the generalised view of the IT investment factors in hotel industry. It may be more appropriate to conduct case method by considering the cultural effect of IT investment in country level. For example, if we compare the international chain hotel's IT investment in Tokyo and in London different results can be reached because of cultural influence. Japanese hotel guests may require more technological advanced hotel equipments than British hotel guests. As the level of technology use can be affected by the cultural phenomenon further researches should consider case study method in order to capture an important observation under cultural context.

5 Facts and Findings

The findings cover a total of 7376 hotel properties in 71 countries. The countries are grouped by its economic status into three levels which are developing, newly industrialised and industrialised (see Appendix 5). There are a total of 46 developing countries, 4 newly industrialised countries and 21 industrialised countries that are covered in this database.

The findings are organised according to the research objectives which are as mentioned before:

4. Understanding IT benefits by identifying both intangible and tangible aspects of IT will affect decision making process.
5. Knowledge and skill of stakeholders highly affect implementation of required innovative technology as a result hotel industry is competitively slower in conducting innovative technology than other industries.
6. Staff training and improving staff skills are the main components of the effective implementation and efficient use of IT.

The chosen frameworks were followed to make research findings. However, to show the connection between findings and hypothesis the author organised findings under three objectives by following the related parts of the frameworks.

5.1 Objective 1

1. Understanding IT benefits by identifying both intangible and tangible aspects of IT will affect decision making process.

Findings related to objective 1 are analysed by evaluating the tangible and intangible aspects of IT. By using Resource based view (RBV) framework, intangible aspects are analysed by IT infrastructure and Information repositories.

5.1.1 Tangible Aspect Evaluation Techniques

The techniques used to evaluate IT investment is analysed under tangible and intangible aspects. The tangible aspects can be evaluated by using financial/mathematical and non-financial methods. Financial methods that are commonly used by hotel executives are return on investment (ROI), payback period (PBP), cost saving analysis and net present value (NPV). The most preferred three techniques among all financial methods were ROI, PBP and cost saving analysis (Suwardy, et al., 2003; Karadag, et al., 2009). When these techniques analysed under corporate and property level, it was found that the financial methods are used significantly more in corporate level hotels than in property level hotels (Karadag et al., 2009). In contrast non-financial techniques that are commonly used are best fit, previous contact, new version and instruction. The most preferred non-financial techniques are best fit, new version and previous contact (Suwardy, et al., 2003; Karadag, et al., 2009). On the other hand, non-financial methods are used significantly more by property level hotels than corporate level hotels (Karadag et al., 2009). When only tangible aspects are calculated the feasibility of the project can be seen as unfeasible. As a result, IT is still seen a cost-generating or 'evil' on the eye of some hotel managers (MacFarlane, 2009). There is one significantly revenue generating streams of IT which is the internet (Denneny, 2009; MacFarlane, 2009). As a result, hotels prioritise internet related IT investment as it provide direct benefits (MacFarlane, 2009).

5.1.2 Intangible aspect evaluation methods

Since it is difficult to estimate the intangible benefits of IT investment they are often ignored. There are two measurements used to tangiblise intangible aspects of IT investment. However, it is crucial to understand IT benefits it is important to identify the benefits, which are the combination of tangible and intangible benefits. One measurement used to measure efficiency of IT investment is data envelopment analysis (DEA). The advantage of this measure is that DEA permits the researcher to use multiple inputs. Barros et al. (2009) conducted longitudinal study that analysed fifteen hotel's technology efficient during 7 years of period by using DEA measurement. As a result thechnology efficiency was not always related to the technology change. The

final result grouped hotels under three efficiency frontiers which are: hotels that were always efficient after a new technology was introduced, hotels that were not efficient after a new technology was introduced and hotels that were always efficient no matter when a new technology was introduced.

Two strategically important benefits of IT can be named as 'to enhance operational performance' and 'to enhance customer satisfaction'. When these two benefits were analysed among developing countries hotel managers, UK managers gave more importance to 'to enhance operational performance' than other countries while USA hotel managers gave more importance to 'to enhance customer satisfaction' than other countries (van Hoof et al., 1996).

Another factor that influences the hotel's perception of strategic importance of IT is the hotel grading and the location. It was found that when the hotel class increase from two-star to five-star the hotel's understanding of strategic value of IT will increase (Camison, 2000; Sahadev et al., 2005). Moreover, the age of the hotel have a high propensity in IT adoption (Sahadev, et al., 2005). New hotels adopt significantly more technology compared to old hotels. Sahadev et al. (2009) analysed hotels under four three ages which are 3-9 years old, 10-15 years old and 15 years old and more. On the other hand, several studies' result showed that the size of the hotel doesn't affect the understanding of IT importance as the size increase doesn't increase the strategic importance of IT value (Camison, 2000; Wei, et al., 2001; Sahadev, et al., 2005). On the other hand, the city hotels showed a clear understanding of IT importance on competitive advantage than sea-side or country hotels (Camison, 2000).

IT Infrastructure

Out of different computer applications, front office applications provided the most influence on the performance of hotels (Ham et al., 2005) as front office and back office technologies are the main areas where technology is widely used (van Hoof, et al., 1996). More specifically hotels invest on PMS, YM, reservation, sales and catering (Cline, 1999). The research conducted by David et al. (1996) found that the installment of the front office applications were considered to improve the productivity in hotels. The efficient use of a front office application allowed the user to provide faster and more efficient service to the guest and as a result the queuing time was reduced and the 36

availability of information benefited guests (Whitaker, 1987). The percentage use of front office and back office technology will differ as the size of hotels change. Small hotels with 15 rooms and less will use 61% back office computers and 18% front office computers (Buick, 2003). While 96% of large hotels use front office application that is followed by use of back office, F&B, Housekeeping and Engineering applications (van Hoof, et al., 1996).

There are some arguments regarding the strategic effect of the guest-oriented applications. Cline (1999) made suggestion that guestroom is the main area where the competitive advantage can be created. It was found that in UK hotels have less guest-oriented devices compared to USA and Canada (van Hoof, et al., 1996). However, the result showed that there are inefficiency of the guest-oriented devices such as "in-room information, vending, and entertainment, as well as automated check-in and check-out devices" (David, et al., 1996; van Hoof, et al., 1996). The result reached by Ham et al. (2005) proving that the guest-oriented devices had no affect on the performance of the hotel. The finding by Law et al. (2005) also concluded that the guest's perception of technology provision decrease from 70% in 1997 to 43% in 2004. In the same study hotel guest evaluated the provision of technology as "sufficient" or "very sufficient", which suggests that the main concern or motivational factor for hotel guest is not the high tech devices in room.

Information Repositories

An information repository is the collection of available data that is required for the strategic decision making process (Piccoli and Ives, 2005). It does not necessarily mean the database or the software that is required to collect data but more likely an information that is unique and necessary to create a competitive advantage. The use of technology can be analysed under using technology to gather information for decision making and to provide information to create competitive advantage.

The use of communication tools such as email, telephone or intranet can benefit hotel management to effectively communicate and to leverage intangible human and business resources. E-mail and ICT is popular communication tool in medium-scaled (100-300 rooms), large-scaled (more than 300 rooms) hotels if hotels are analysed by size, and four and five-star hotels if hotels are analysed by star grading (Wei, et al., 2001; Sahadev 37

et al., 2005). The use of ICT showed a significant affect on the budgetary performance of the departmental managers (Winata, et al., 2005). The research found that the manager's use of ICT had a positive affect on the budgetary participation.

Hotels spent 3.1% of their revenue on IT investment (Cline, 1999). However, the use of IT in hospitality can differ between different hotel categories. The use of the internet or the level of computerization is highly related to the size of the hotel. Internet is widely used by almost all large-scaled hotels (91.8%) to advertise and promote their business (Law, et al., 2005). In contrast, only 68% of small scale hotels located in rural areas use internet for business purpose (Buick, 2003). However, the use of the internet to receive reservation has changed from 4% in 1999 (Cline, 1999) to 20% in 2001 (Wei et al., 2001), which is higher than the prediction (11%) made by Cline (1999). The use of a web-based reservation is highly related to the category of the hotels. As hotel star rating increases, the preferance of the web-based reservation will increase. For example, five-star hotels used more (91.7%) web-based reservations than four-star hotels (61%) (Daghfous, et al., 2009).

5.2 Objective 2

2. Knowledge and skill of stakeholders highly affect implementation of required innovative technology as a result hotel industry is competitively slower in conducting innovative technology than other industries.

Findings related to objective 2 are analysed by underlining two IT capabilities of RBV framework which are management skill and relationship asset. Relationship asset is analysed in depth by conducting stakeholder's analysis. The main six stakeholders identified are owners, managers, government, suppliers, employees and customers.

Management Skills

Management skill is the ability of the managers to understand IT functions, the organizational requirements and technical requirements (Ross, et al., 1996). The use of technology in management level will differ as of the hotel characteristics. To enhance IT knowledge and skills of the managers the training is essential to enhance the strategic and tactical value of IT. The technological ability of the managers cannot 38

be sufficient even in industrialised countries. The study conducted by van Hoof et al. (1996) stated that managers of different hotel categories in UK evaluated their technological ability lower than hotel managers in USA and Canada. This result was a consequence of lack of training that UK managers received. However, the interview result from MacFarlane (2009) and Sabir (2009) concluded that luxury and five-star hotels in UK provide all level of trainings when new technology is implemented. On the other hand, the main managerial-related reasons that affected small hotels to use less IT was identified as a lack of IT knowledge, older management and financial constraint (Main, 1995; Buhalis, et al., 1998).

For a clear understanding of decision making and adoption process of IT, certain strategic departments and main decision makers can be identified. Cline (2001) lists the main decision makers of IT projects in hospitality industry which are Chief financial officer (CFO), Chief information officer (CIO), Chief executive officer (CEO), General Manager (GM) and Chief operation officer (COO). On the other hand Fink (2003) identifies the key stakeholders who are not only representatives from senior management but also lower level representatives such as line managers and end-users. Ross and Weill (2002) mentions that the IT executives are the right people to make decision regarding IT management as it involves the choice of technology, the design of IT operations and the requirement of technical expertise. However, as far as the financial side of IT investment is concerned the final decision is mainly made by CFO (Fink, 2003). However, these findings were contradicting with the results of interview with Denny (2009) and Sabir (2009). IT investment decisions are made by CIO, who is the board level representative of large hotel chains (more than 300 rooms). While luxury independent hotel's IT investment decision making can be finalised by finance executive (MacFarlane, 2009). In contrast, in small or property level hotels decision making is mainly done by hotel owners or finance executives (MacFarlane, 2009).

It is important to have a written IT strategy that compliments the business strategy. When the IT strategy is concerned four-star hotels are leading five-star hotels with its written and formal IT strategy (Daghfous et al., 2009). However, manager's experience and education level were higher in five-star hotels than four-star hotels (Daghfous et al., 2009). The educational level is considered to have a direct influence on considering IT importance. However, it has contrary in this case as the five-star 39

hotels with more educated and experienced managers have less written and formal IT strategy than four-star hotels.

Relationship Asset

Relationship assets is a mutual respect and trust between IT management and business units (Ross et al., 1996). It is difficult and complicated to find the balance between the different interests of the authorities as not all decisions are made by considering the mutual benefit for all stakeholders.

The main stakeholders were identified by author and their level of influence was measured by author by considering their level of power and level of interest. As shown in Figure 6 the main stakeholders that have influence on IT investment decision making were identified as owners, managers, employees, hotel guests, government and institutional customers (suppliers of technological equipments).

Owners can be managers as well in independent hotels. The problem with the owners can be related to their level of experience and management knowledge to select, install and operate the required technology. This statement is related to the owner's power of influence which is higher in hotels managed in the property level than in the corporate level (Orfila-Sintes et al., 2005). Owners can demonstrate lack of marketing and managerial skills which influences the IT investment decision making process (Buhalis et al., 1998). O'Connor and Murphy (2004) highlight the data-ownership dilemma of data management that can be caused by the structure of hotel industry in which owners, management companies and brands fail to cooperate together.

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Figure 6: Stakeholder analysis

Source: Self Annotated.

Managers can have a high influence on the IT investment decision making process. However, their level of power is less than the owner's level of power as they can't finance the projects. The main factor that influences the efficient use of IT tool is the knowledge and professionalism of both the managers and the operating staff (van Hoof *et al.*, 1996). Fink (2003) determines that the key success factor to benefit from IT investment is the management role of "effective communications, transparency and recognition of diversity". Furthermore, Ross and Weill (2002) makes more detailed statement identifying the organizational gaps of IT implementation which are relationship between management hierarchy and junior hotel staff in relation to IT utilization, misunderstanding the limitations of the company's IT and business resources, and lack of IT department's involvement in the decision making process. Decision making process in large hotel chains such as Hilton, Jumeirah or Starwood is heavily centralised and made in board level (MacFarlane, 2009; Sabir, 2009). In this situation, the main role of IT managers will be to evaluate the technology benefits and make recommendation (MacFarlane, 2009). As managers pay more interest to efficiency and productivity of the operations their level of interest to invest in IT to enhance service productivity is higher than other stakeholders. Moreover, from the interview with Denny (2009) and MacFarlane (2009) it was also noticed that hotel's

executives are aware of technological replacement of paper works and effect on energy savings.

Institutional customers are the partner companies and suppliers that require up-to-date information in order to provide better IT related services and to follow the system condition of the hotels in order to advice to improvement and update information. Moreover, Whitaker (1987) argues the importance of suppliers to improve the understanding of IT in the hotel and catering business. However, only 19% of hotels use extranet to get connected to their suppliers (Cline, 1999). Furthermore, it was found that 32% of the hotels acquire technology equipments from the suppliers but they do update and modification by themselves instead of accepting supplier's service (Jacob and Groizard, 2007). However, suppliers' collaboration is required during purchase, instalment and training process. Within the hotels that collaborate with their suppliers closely, medium and large-scaled hotels use emails more often to communicate with their suppliers (Jacob & Groizard, 2007). On the other hand, corporate level hotels have failed to maximise potential of their current IT application because of lack of independent advices from suppliers (Main, 1995). However, the interest level of supplier's is high because they are interested to provide service in order to enhance their revenue.

Another interesting point is the government influence on the selection of technology for transfer. The level of tourism development can be affected by the political environment and other lobby groups of the country (Pine, 1992; Buhalis et al., 1998). Technology transfer can widely differ between developing, newly industrialised and industrialised countries as the level of governemtn influence may differ. The IT infrastructure of the country will influence the use of technology in hotels. According to Pine (1992), developing country's government will not support hotels to use the latest technology as it may influence the unemployment level. Technology use can be understood as replacing humans by computers. In some cases government may engourage use of technology if used technology is more labour intensive technology rather than profit increasing that can attract foreign investment (Pine, 1992). On ther other hand, in industrialised countries the hotel and tourism is recognised as significant revenue generating industries as it attracts more tourist. Therefore, it is government responsibility to study the feasibility of the hotel investment carefully to understand the

require amount of infrastructure to reach international level of quality. Government is also a main body that affects the level of education provided in nation. So it is government's and owner's responsibility to cooperate closely to have a mutual interest for an adequate training, staff skill development and infrastructure development. This can be more strategically important for the small and medium size hotels as they don't have economy of scale to provide training and hire educated and skilled staff (Buhalis and Main, 1998). As a result, government have a high influence/power for the IT investment but lower interest level of innovative technology.

Customer relationship can be considered as one of the main area where the technology is used to understand customers and to provide information to customer to retain their loyalty (O'Connor and Murphy, 2004; Daghfous and Barkhi, 2009). Developing close relationship with each customer by using innovative technologies such as CRM, SCM and PMS, enable hotels to reduce the substitutes and decrease the transactional costs (O'Connor and Murphy, 2004). There are different methods used to gather information from the guests. An in-room questionnaire is still the most commonly used method that is followed by mail survey, in-room TV survey, telephone survey and computerised survey (Cline, 1999). On the other hand, the quality of information and the usefulness of information is significant to make the required decisions. Information quality is the most affective factor that influence the level of technology used (Kim et al., 2005).

However, when the decision making takes place the customer segments do not have a significant effect on the technology used (Denneny, 2009). There are several reasons hotels consider before adopting any technology. One of the reasons is related to hotel segment. As hotel segment changes the priority of investment decision making will change. Luxury hotel segments pay more importance to adopt technology to improve the guest service, staff efficiency and increase revenue while convention hotels adopted more technology to improve productivity of employees (Siquaw, et al., 2000; Denneny, 2009; MacFarlane, 2009). However, convention and casino hotels led by number of technologies adopted to improve guest service compare to other hotel segments (Siquaw et al., 2000). As the result, guest service is one of the main reasons of IT investment in luxury hotel segments. According to MacFarlane (2009) guest's expectation is always high and same for all type of hotels. However, as the guest

doesn't have direct affect on decision making process the power level of guest is low but the interest level is moderate.

5.3 Objective 3

3. Staff training and improving staff skills are the main components of the effective implementation and efficient use of IT.

Findings related to objective 3 are examined by employee skills that is further analysed by conducting Decomposed Theory of Planned Behaviour (DTPB) to identify the main factors that influence employee's willingness toward the adoption of a new technology.

Employee Skills

Employee skills are the technical skills that is required for the effective use of IT. Whitaker (1987) stated that the ultimate barriers for the successful IT implementation is related to the skill, training and ability. Skills can be enhanced through training or experience.

The training that is provided by hotels can be categorised under in-house trainings such as on-the-job, course-based or training in group, and off-site trainings such as conferences, workshops or e-learning programmes. The most common method of trainings are in-house trainings which are on-the-job training (95%) and coursed-based training (57%) (Law, et al., 2005; Jacob, et al., 2006; MacFarlane, 2009; Sabir, 2009). The significant difference in training can be identified between four- and five-star hotels. Four-star hotels show more efforts (78.5%) by sending employees to the workshops and conferences than five-star hotels (72.2%) (Daghfous et al., 2009). On the other hand, five-star hotels overrule four-star hotels on hiring consultant, spending supply chain management (SCM) related training and knowldege acquisition and sending employees to SCM-related conferences and workshops (Daghfous et al., 2009). However, the common problems faced by large-scaled hotels during the training will be related to the organization of the training sessions regarding the resouce, budget and time constraints (Law et al., 2005; Sabir, 2009; Sirvan, 2009).

Large-scale hotels in corporate level adopt same level of technology in order to keep the synergy. As a result the trainer of new technology will have schedule to visit each hotel in different locations. According to Corbett (2009) IT managers don't have authority to decide on the trainer. The training period can be considered as not enough or not effective enough for the short period of time that trainer will visit hotels (Sabir, 2009).

Employee skills and educational level is directly related to the economic status of the country. As industrialised countries spend more on educational system than developing or newly industrialised countries, hotel employees in industrialised countries require less training or guidance compared to the developing and newly industrialised countries (Pine, 1992). As a result, the presence of a training manager, a training room and the existence of a training department are less common in hotels in industrialised country (Pine, 1992). In comparison, hotels in developing country will require higher operational budget for the training programmes than hotels in industrialised country.

The study by Pine (1992) shows that the technology transfer in hotels is related to the brand and management of the hotel. If hotel is part of the international chain, the probability of having more professional training programme with the more experienced management team will increase (Pine, 1992). In comparison, small independent hotels with the less than 50 rooms have management with the poor IT knowledge and the training programmes that is not available in the most (78%) of the properties (Main, 1995; Buhalis et al., 1998).

Decomposed Theory of Planned Behaviour

Employees with perception about the technological usefulness will consider their daily tasks as a competible and will have willingness to perform better (Lam et al., 2007; Huh et al., 2009). Moreover, the DTPB model tells us the effect of social pressure on routine use of IT. Those social pressures can be caused by superiors or the team members. Finally, self-efficacy and technical support are considered as significant predictors of perceived behavioral control (Huh et al., 2009). It explains that when employees are more confident and familiar with the new technology they are more willing to use and accept a new technology (Huh et al., 2009). Therefore, the effect of training will boost the knowledge and skill of using new technology which will result 45

in increase in confidentiality of employees. As employees are more confident they illustrate positive attitude and willingness to adopt new technology (Huh et al., 2009).

5. Analysis

This chapter analyses findings by interpreting the meaning of finding. The main focus will be on three research objectives which are

1. Understanding IT security by identifying how employees perceive aspects of IT security policies within the IT department
2. Knowledge of the role of information security in the organization and the impact of security policies on employees' performance
3. How having a positive attitude towards IT security affects employees' willingness to adopt IT security measures

The analysis of the data will be done by using the content analysis method. The content analysis method is a research method for identifying and describing the meaning of words, symbols, or gestures. It is a method for identifying and describing the meaning of words, symbols, or gestures. It is a method for identifying and describing the meaning of words, symbols, or gestures.

5.1 Understanding IT security by identifying how employees perceive aspects of IT security policies within the IT department

The first objective of this study is to understand how employees perceive aspects of IT security policies within the IT department. This objective is achieved by analyzing the data collected from the IT department. The data shows that employees have a positive attitude towards IT security policies. They are willing to adopt IT security measures and they are confident in the IT department. This is a positive finding as it indicates that employees are more confident in the IT department and they are willing to adopt IT security measures. This is a positive finding as it indicates that employees are more confident in the IT department and they are willing to adopt IT security measures.

6 Analysis

This chapter analyses findings by interpreting the meaning of finding. The main focus will be on three research objectives which are:

1. Understanding IT benefits by identifying both intangible and tangible aspects of IT will affect decision making process.
2. Knowledge and skill of stakeholders highly affect implementation of required innovative technology as a result hotel industry is competitively slower in conducting innovative technology than other industries.
3. Staff training and improving staff skills are the main components of the effective implementation and efficient use of IT.

The strategic use of IT in hotel industry will be questioned in order to understand the attitude of hotel management toward IT investment. The analysis will provide information about the competitiveness of IT, the importance of IT as a strategic tool and the potential of IT as a tool to sustain competitive advantage.

6.1 Understanding hotel's investment priorities

From the findings it can be understand the sophisticated IT evaluation methods are widely used in hotel industry to evaluate the IT investment. The decision making process may significantly involve the evaluation of tangible benefits. The measurement methods used are the reflection of the decision making process which affects technology improvement. The main reason of using ROI as an evaluation method can be related to the ability of the method to identify the costs and benefits of the investment (Karadag et al., 2009). In order to analyze the value of investment by the length of time PBP method is used as a second preferred method. All hotel types commonly use best fit method as non-financial method to examine the competitiveness of different systems used in hotels. There are different systems used by the different department of the hotels. For example, front office, sales, and marketing use Property Management Systems such as FIDELIO or OPERA while food and beverage department use MICROS. As different systems are used in different department it is important to test the competitiveness of the systems to each other. The result shows that hotels in property level use more financial methods than hotels in corporate level. It can

be related to the number of experts available to use these sophisticated evaluation methods. Management skills and educational level has affect on the use of the evaluation methods. As the small hotel managers' educational level and skills are relatively lower than large hotels' managers, more non-financial methods such as best fit or advice from contacts are commonly used than financial methods. However, it is not enough to evaluate the contribution of IT investment by analyzing its financial benefits.

There are many intangible IT benefits can be listed that help managers to understand why they need to invest a huge amount of money every year. It was noted that the main reason of IT investment in hotels is to maintain competitive level parity with their competitors (Sabir, 2009). It can be more effective to identify intangible benefits of IT before evaluating tangible benefits of IT because it can affect the critical aspects of the decision making process (Karadag et al., 2009). However, from the evaluation of technical benefits can overcome the evaluation of non-technical benefits. It is hard to measure non-technical or intangible benefits of IT as there is no clear identification of the inputs and outputs. The measurement of intangible benefits is more sophisticated than measurement of tangible benefits. It can observed that not much literatures mention the intangible benefit measurement method which can be related to the not popularity of these measurement and difficulty to conduct it. Barros et al. (2009) conducted DEA to measure the efficiency of IT investment by analyzing hotels during seven years of period. The main concern related to IT investment is the extensiveness of payback time. The result showed that for the valid conclusion, the researcher need to conduct DEA as it provides a flexibility to include relevant inputs and outputs (Shafer et al., 2000). Technological efficiency is explained as a distribution of best-practice technology for management activities (Barros et al., 2009). The efficiency measurement will help hotel management not only analyze the efficiency use of technology but to better manage investment and to understand the requirement of technical experts.

Hotels can have different priorities to make investment in technology. The main two priorities that were identified were to improve operational efficiency and to improve customer service. The priority of the benefits can change according to strategic value. When one level of requirement is fulfilled the hotel management prioritizes the next

level of requirement. The main purpose of UK hotel manager's priority to improve operational efficiency was related to the need for better technology. On the other hand, the next level of priority for USA managers was to provide better service to their customers. As a result, UK managers will invest more on operational level technology while USA managers will invest more on customer relations technologies such as CRM.

There are some external factors that affect IT investment in hotel industry. The market size, age and the location of the hotel play an important role in understanding the strategic importance of IT. If hotels are grouped according to their strategic attitudes hotels located in cities can show high propensity to adopt new technology which can be related to the high competition in well-developed locations with a large market size. However, old hotels located in cities can show lower technological propensity compared with the new hotels located in cities. This can be related to the popularity and how known the hotel is. The age of a hotel can indicate that a hotel has already achieved a significant reputation among its customers. As a result, new hotels will need to make more effort to retain customers by investing in new and more sophisticated technologies such as CRM or PMS.

The result of the previous studies showed that the size doesn't affect the understanding of IT importance. But it can be better analysed by identifying the level of IT applications used in small hotels and large hotels. The main application that showed affect on productivity of hotel was considered as front office application. However, only 18% of small hotels use front office application compared to 96% of large hotels. This result shows that small hotels are not aware of the importance of IT applications as front office application can be considered as basic application for effective hotel management. The communications tools are significantly more used by medium-scale and large-scale hotels than small-scaled hotels. According to MacFarlane (2009) this result is related to the economic scale of the hotel and hotel management knowledge about technology benefits.

The interesting result was reached regarding guest-oriented technologies. Guest-oriented technologies had showed no effect on hotel efficiency in USA hotels where the manager's main priority is to improve guest service. However, the efficient use of these

applications by guest can increase guest satisfaction. The benefits of communication tools such as emails, telephone or intranet will be contribution on decision making process such as budgetary related. Increase in guest satisfaction can influence increase in service quality which can be measured by using SERVQUAL measurement method (Pitt et al., 1995). However, in order to get an effective result from investing in guest-oriented application hotel management should train staff to use this application in order to support use of these devices by guest. As a result mutual understanding will be reached by more effectively sharing information.

6.2 Stakeholder's affect on decision making process

Understanding the importance of technology by executive management and other stakeholder result is the main reason of lack of improvement in technology used in hotel industry. The result shows that management understanding of IT benefits cannot be analysed by the economic status of the country. There is no difference between industrialised, newly industrialised and developing countries. The main management-related barriers were concerning technology knowledge, educational level and age (Daghfous et al., 2009). However, management-related reasons can have different effects when hotels are analysed by property level and corporate level hotels (MacFarlane, 2009). As the decision making is heavily centralised in corporate level hotels (Whitaker, 1987) especially large chain hotels the technological knowledge of executive managers have less affect compared with the hotels in property level especially small-scaled hotels. However, the importance of written IT strategy is less recognized in five-star hotels than four-star hotels. Five-star hotels with the relatively higher economy of scale that endow reasonably enough resource, may be the reason why they may not require to have a clear strategic path compared to four-star hotels that require to specify a core capabilities such as IT capability (Daghfous et al., 2009).

Ownership dilemma which is the case of USA hotel industry is related to the failure of cooperation between owners and managers. This is caused by the same level of right given to ownership, management companies and brands to use customer data (O'Connor, et al., 2004). As a result customer relationship management (CRM) has failed to be efficient as stakeholders failed to work cooperatively. Instead of cooperation these three stakeholders may even begin compete with each other which

will affect implementation of CRM system (O'Connor et al., 2004). However, as CRM is still considered as a strategic tool by USA hotels to differentiate themselves from their competitors (Daghfous et al., 2009).

The failure of small-scale hotels to understand a strategic importance of IT can be related to the relationship with their suppliers. Suppliers should see small-scale hotels as a potential customer that will invest in IT application if the required amount of information and knowledge are provided. The result of the findings show that only medium and large-scale hotels give importance to supplier relationship by conducting communication tools such as emails and only 19% of hotels use extranet to communicate with their suppliers. In the case of small hotels, it can be understood that suppliers' marketing tool to approach small-scale hotels is not effective as the main reason identified by small-scale hotels to fail to understand IT importance was the lack of independent advice which should be provided by suppliers.

Government influence is especially important for the developing countries. Not only IT infrastructure is important but also a tourism and hotel institutions that support tourism development and represent hotel industry in government level are required. However, the dilemma between government interest and hospitality industry interest can affect IT improvement in hotels. However, government's role should support the economy of country by supporting the investment in technology and hospitality. Hospitality industry is labour-intensive industry where the boost of investment will affect the employment level as a result the economy will improve.

6.3 Human Barriers

Human barrier is one of the critical attribute of IT implementation in hospitality industry. As it is unavoidable management should understand the importance of training to improve the technical skills and knowledge of staff to use technology effectively and efficiently. The most common and the most effective training used by hotels is on-the-job training (Law et al., 2005; Jacob et al., 2006; MacFarlane, 2009; Sabir, 2009). The significance of on-the-job training is it allows employees to learn the required job tool by practice. It can be considered as an effective training method during implementation of a new technology (Corbett, 2009). However, in the most

cases the main training used by chain hotels before implementation of a new technology is e-learning programmes or training conferences, which lack of practice. It was mentioned by Corbett (2009) that Jumeirah hotels also adopted conference training that could be more effective is combined or overlapped with the on-the-job training.

Because of different economic development, different countries have different level of educated population. In developing countries, hotel managers can have difficulty to find staff with technical skills (Pine, 1992). However, as the availability of skilled staff decreases hotels will require more training facilities which is evidenced by the results of findings (Daghfous et al., 2009). Moreover, training can be considered as a motivational factor that increase employee's willingness to adopt a new technology. By analysing employee behaviour the author provides better understand how employee perceive technology adoption, which can be used to strategically manage IT implementation and development. As a result shows, to increase employee perception of IT acceptance hotel managers should emphasize all aspects of implementation process. This includes increase employee familiarity by providing sufficient amount of training, providing support from supervisors and managers, provide sufficient amount of technical support to increase their willingness of using a new technology (Huh et al., 2009).

Category	Sub-category
1. Training	1.1. On-the-job training
2. Support	2.1. Technical support
3. Familiarity	3.1. Familiarity with technology
4. Motivation	4.1. Motivation to learn
5. Management	5.1. Management support
6. Technical	6.1. Technical support
7. Supervisors	7.1. Supervisors support
8. Managers	8.1. Managers support
9. Technical support	9.1. Technical support
10. Willingness	10.1. Willingness to use

7 Conclusion

This research reviewed IT investment in hospitality industry from evaluation and investment perspectives. Based on the objectives of the research the author developed an integrative analysis by conducting three frameworks which are Resource Based View (RBV), stakeholder analysis and Decomposed Theory of Planned Behavior (DTPB). The structure of analysis was related to the review of the 24 literatures IT related hospitality industry researches. The main focus was to understand the strategic IT investment in hotel industry by analysis IT investment decision making process under seven hotel characteristics.

The main conclusions of the findings are analysed under Table 5. The table was created by the author in order to visually present the main conclusions of the research. The table was the result of the decision making process of different hotel characteristics toward innovative technology. Hotels that give strategic priority to IT investment were shown under 'more innovative' title while hotels that give less priority to IT investment were shown under 'less innovative' title.

Table 4: Comparison of hotel innovation by characteristic of hotels

More innovative	Less innovative
Large-scale	Small-scale
Luxury	Condo-villa, standard, budget
Chain	Independent
Five-star	Four-star
Industrialised country	Developing country
Newer hotels	Olders hotels
Intensive competition	Less intensive competition
Corporate level	Property level
Urban area	Rural area
More experienced IT managers	Less experienced IT managers

Moreover, the dynamic relationship between stakeholders is analysed to critically relate the influence of each stakeholder in decision making process. As a result, the main and the most powerful stakeholder were identified as owners, managers and government. Not only identification was important but how each stakeholder's decisions effect IT investment was important. These initiatives can be considered as a critical point during the evaluation process. Some interesting points were made regarding supplier and small-scale hotel's attitude toward IT investment. Small-scale hotels can be seen as a potential buyer of IT application if both supplier and owners will make afford toward understanding these potentials.

The main barrier of implementation process was identified as human related barrier and investigated by conducting DTPB model. According to DTPB the drivers of the human related barriers were identified as social pressure, familiarity and self-efficacy. The understanding of these drivers is important for the effective IT implementation and efficient use of technology. The author believes the findings will provide useful structure to be followed by hotel executives for IT investment decision making.

8 Recommendations

The following recommendations are aimed towards the executives in hospitality industry.

- As IT investment involve some tangible aspects that can require high amount monetary investment and intangible aspects that are difficult to identify it is crucial for any management to understand the main benefits and the capacity of organisation to be able to use these benefits efficiently. As the dilemma of IT investment concern, it can be recommended for hotel executives to understand the capacity of the organisation by analysing IT infrastructure and technical skills of staff to make a decision.
- The priority of IT investment can be related to the requirement of organisation. However, different objectives will require different amount of investment. The main concern should be related to the strategy role of technology to enhance business.
- IT should be used as a strategic tool to improve the communication in all levels of organisation. The feedback should come from top to down and down to top. For example, it was mentioned in the text that efficient use of information and communication technology (ICT) will affect the budgetary decision making process in hotel industry. However, it was found that only 19% of hotels use ICT to communicate with their suppliers.
- The key IT benefit is related to the data management and knowledge management. There are some very know and useful technologies used in hotels to improve their customer service relationship by using CRM and PMS systems. By using these technologies hotels can reach each customer and provide a unique service especially for the individual guest.
- Management difficulties related to training concern the money and time spent on training. Labour intensive nature of hotel industry and high turnover of staff are inseparable parts of the hotel industry. As far as IT investment is concerned, the training programmes for the use of the system may be more important than the actual implementation of physical technology. Since technology without proper use is not use.

9 Reflections

The study enabled the researcher to make a variable conclusions and comments. The fact and finding part can be structured by following the framework that was chosen. However, as the priority of answering the objectives of the research concerned the author decided to follow structure by analysing objectives rather than using the framework properly. If author followed the structure of framework then the analysis part could look differently. The main difference is related to the visualising the framework. In this case, the fact and findings and as well as analysis part could follow the structure of RBV framework which analyse IT asset and IT capability of by defining IT infrastructure, IT repositories, technical skill, management skill and relationship asset.

The analysis part provides different perspectives to be further investigated such as the supplier relationship, small hotel's IT investment decision making and effective training process. As recommended in previous chapter the further analysis can be related to supplier's understanding of a potential users or IT.

As the study was conducted in a relatively short period of time there were no opportunities to conduct case study analysis of IT investment in hotel industry. The case study method can be considered as very effective method to be used as it investigated the research area in depth which is required in this case as well. The main concern of the author is to analyse the cultural effect on the adoption propensity of IT.

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11.1 Algorithm 1: hotel category segmentation

The above main characteristics are distributed in the following way. First category
Hotels are hotels by its relevant theme such as business, hotel services,
delicious food, spa, room, conversion, online marketing, credits and B2B.
London is the category that hotels belong under any hotels. Second hotel and
country factor. The category is derived from the country category as the country
category provides the geographic status of each country while hotel type categories
provide more the homogeneity of hotels without identifying the location of the hotel.
Based on the classification of the hotel by its geographical location, there are hotels
in different parts of the world. In general, hotels are classified into three main
categories: luxury, economy and budget. Each category is further divided into
sub-categories. The luxury category is further divided into the range of the
hotel or rooms in the hotel. This is the most sophisticated method to identify the
hotel size. The main purpose of the classification of the hotel is to identify
luxury, economy, business and other. Each category is further divided into
sub-categories by size, room and is given and provided by various features of a
country or other additional information. There are many 3 star hotels of the hotel
will be a 4 star hotel. The 4 star hotels are more and more. The 4 star hotels
in the economy category are in the 4 star category and other 4 star hotels are in
the economy where the hotels are located. There are many similar group categories
that are given and provided and restricted.

11 Appendices

11.1 Appendix 1 - Hotel category explanations

The seven main characteristics are constructed in the following way. *Type* is category that assigns hotels by its relevant theme such as full-service, limited service, conference, resort, suite, motel, convention, casino, conference, standard and B&B. *Location* is the category that groups hotels under city hotels, sea-side hotels and country hotels. This category is different from the country category as the country category identified the economic status of each country while hotel type categorises hotels under the functionality of hotels without identifying the location of the hotel. *Brand* is the classification of the hotel by its operations in the market. Here the hotels are classified under independently operated hotels and chain hotels. Chain hotels are analysed under domestic and international groups. *Size* indicates the number of the beds or rooms in the hotel. This is the most commonly used method to signify the hotel size. *Segments* indicate the value-added sector of the hotel such as luxury, upscale, midscale, economy and budget. *Class/Category* is the hotel category measurement by star rating that is given and controlled by Tourism Authority of a country or other authorised organisation. There are totally 5 star ratings of the hotel which are one-star hotel, two-star, three-star, four-star and five-star. *Country* category in this research doesn't refer to the whole country but refers to the economic status of the country where the hotels are located. These economic statuses group countries into developing, newly industrialised and industrialised.

11.2 Appendix 2 - Interviewees

Grant MacFarlane, IT Systems Manager at Royal Garden Hotel London

- Research: Interview
- Date: 26th Feb 2010
- Duration: 0:47:50 minutes

Jawad Sabir, Assistant IT Manager at Jumeirah Carlton Tower London

- Research: Interview
- Date: 28th Feb 2010
- Duration: 0:18:15 (together with Mr. Elliot Corbett)

Elliot Corbett, IT Manager at Jumeirah Carlton Tower London

- Research: Interview
- Date: 28th Feb 2010
- Duration: 0:18:15 (together with Mr. Jawad Sabir)

Gerard Denny, Hotel Manager at Jumeirah Carlton Tower London

- Research: Interview
- Date: 27th Feb 2010
- Duration: 0:22:12

Guilherme Mayhoffer, Front Office, Receptionist at Jumeirah Carlton Tower London

- Research: Interview
- Date: 30th Jan 2010
- Duration: 0:11:34

11.3 Appendix 3 - Interview Questions

1. It's been found that hotel industry adopt competitively less technology innovation than other industries. What you think the main factors and reasons for this?
2. How often does your hotel invest in new technology?
3. Did a new technology improve the hotel efficiency and guest service?
4. Do you think the new IT effect the efficiency of the staffs?
5. What are the management purposes of the IT investments?
6. As IT Manager, do you think other departmental managers understand the impact of IT on the operation and support the IT investments?
7. Do you consider technology investment is a necessity for the business transactions or a tool to create competitive advantage?
8. Do you think IT is the cost generating department or strategically important department?
9. As IT projects involve a large amount of investment the final decision is mainly made by the Chef Finance Officer rather than Chef Information Officer. What is the authority level of IT manager to make organizational level IT decisions in your hotel?
10. What was the greatest challenge faced before and after IT investment?
11. As the different system gets connected there is need for the compatibility of those systems with each other. Have you tasted the compatibility or have you installed systems that are compatible with each other?
12. Do you think Head Office pay enough attention to improve the IT implementation process by providing the adequate amount of training or there are still some training is required for better use of a new technology?

11.4 Appendix 4 – Interview meeting minutes

Mr. Grant Macfarlane, IT Manager of Royal Garden Hotel. 26/02/2010, 10.00am.

0:47:50 minutes

01:30	IT department can be seen as a cost generating department rather than the profit generating on the eye of less experienced managers or owner in independent hotels or board level where there is no IT representative.
02:00	Depending on the organizational structure the reporting of IT managers can differ. For example, in independent hotels IT managers report to Finance Director rather than executives who responsible for the overall IT operation.
03:30	Hotels invest more in technologies that will provide quicker benefit such as internet technologies. This decision is related to the revenue generation stream of the internet technology. These technologies also got revenue generating potential compared to the other property related technologies as the customers can benefit directly and the payment for the service can be taken as well.
04:40	The hardware such as desktop can be replaced every three or four and half years.
08:00	It is always hard to find the technically skilled staff. But in most of the cases employees are familiar with the technology used. However, senior level manager may lack the technology knowledge because of age constraints.
09:30	Less training is done in terms of office productivity such as general PC but from period to period some specific training can take place in supervisory levels.
10:10	Training is mostly the case when the specific software is introduced. There will be facility provided, the trainer and the time spent for the training. For the new team members hotel provide induction period where the training for the software will take time.
11:30	Some hotels provide computer-based facilities that are located in different departments. However, in the case of Royal Garden Hotel this kind of facilities are not provided but was offered to Board Level and have rejected so far.
12:35	IT investments are evaluated and recommended by IT manager whose decisions are not affected by the skill and knowledge of other departmental managers.
14:00	The executive who is responsible for the IT investment is Finance Director in independent luxury hotel.
14:45	IT is seen as necessity but same time a cost center rather than a central part of the business. So one role of the IT managers is to try to change the culture of the organization and attitude of the other senior managers who responsible for the IT investment decision making.
16:50	"There is more scope of change in terms of upgrade needs in terms of efficiencies and lifecycle management. There is a distinct lack of available investment. So it becomes a case of prioritization."

17:30	"Cost benefit analysis and return on investment can be done to evaluate IT projects. However, because of lack of IT buyers in Board level and lack of IT seniors in Board level and lack of available capital the required amount of projects will not be undertaken."
18:10	Introducing an innovative technology such as work flow management or paperless office this can benefit organisation by reducing the overhead and reduce the staff amount which will reduce the cost as a result.
19:30	The culture of the organization can limit the implementation of innovative technology. For example, luxury hotels are more human oriented.
20:00	In corporate level they can benefit from the centralized department.
23:50	For the luxury hotel the image of the organisation is main priority. So in order to cut cost they don't prefer to use IT as an option and cut number of employees as a result of computerization.
26:30	Outsourcing IT can be a solution to use the knowledge of more professional experts. However, in case of hotel it is office administration and networking and leadership concerned. Totally outsourcing a whole department can be a case of corporate level decision rather than independent hotel decision.
28:40	As chain hotels they have an economic scale that is hard to be reached by independent hotels. So outsourcing IT can be beneficial.
30:00	Quarter million pounds is spent for IT investment every year in terms of maintenance and purchasing of technology. IT investment is the part of the whole investments that create the five star experiences.
33:45	IT investment can be highly affected by the overall renovation process. As the hotel renovates their rooms the in-room technology is changed as well.
35:30	Security reasons are the important factors that affect the technology transfer.
36:35	Guest training and employee training is important for the implementation process.
38:50	The hotel guest segment affects the use of the technology. So the introduction of new technology can be not effective is guests doesn't want to use or doesn't know how to use. So strategy can be revised.
39:30	When the IT investment is considered long-term usage is considered. So sometimes very technologically advanced rooms can face lack of understanding from guest and employee view point.
41:30	Guests always have high expectation from the technology no matter where they are staying. But there are certain types of guests who prefer to use high technology. Businessmen who spend long time away from home expect to have home technology available in their hotel room.
43:10	Expectation of technology is same for all type of hotels.
44:00	It is important to have provider of the service that are available 24 hours and experts who can speak different language.
46:00	The customer segment affects the IT investment decision. As the market changes the expectation will change as well.

Mr. Gerard Denny, Hotel Manager of Jumeirah Carlton Tower. 27/02/10,

16.00pm. 0:22:12 minutes

01:00	Technology does not seen as a tool of competitive advantage but as a necessity to have an efficient operation as all hotels use similar technologies.
02:00	Technology improvement has affected the hotel efficiency. For example, it enabled Jumeirah to set-up packages like treatment in the spa and solves problems in check out. It also incorporates an automatic authorisation for credit cards through the PMS instead of using two separate systems.
03:00	From operational perspective advanced technology provides operational flexibility, greater knowledge about business, better customer relationship and management facilities. Regarding sales and marketing it provides better statistics and greater flexibility to set up packages.
03:45	At a senior company level there is IT representative (CIO) but not in Board level. Regarding hotel there is hotel representative at a group executive level of the company.
05:00	Internet is the significant revenue generator in some hotels as they charge guests while in some hotels it is free. Most of the IT related technologies are cost related rather than revenue but this technology is necessity not something optional.
06:15	The main reason for the technology investment was the previous technology that was expired.
06:35	Decision making process is very detailed as it includes the implementation and testing of the different choice of the softwares in pilot hotel and if it is not successful they prefer other software. For example HIS system was chosen and tested in one of the hotels. As it was not successful they decided to use Opera system.
08:35	Hotels also choose technology to provide better guest service. It is not only technology driven but most of the time service driven for better communication and to provide better information. Not only the main systems are changing but more and more technology is used for certain departments which are specific for that department. For example, concierge and health club related software systems.
09:30	For the training of the staff in-house training is preferred with the special training room and track of training everyday. Trainers are provided from Opera or from the software company. The whole transition can take over a month depending on the volume of the project.
10:30	The training was provided in all levels covering all users of the new system.
11:45	Even the other hotels implemented the same systems and they had some experience already they faced some challenges that was not expected to happen. But in most cases hotel managers don't prefer to mention those problems in detail.
12:15	There is no specific technology implementation regarding the market segment of the hotel guests.
12:50	The system implementation is seen as a requirement even it is expensive hotels will spend money. However, when it is needed they will prefer to avoid the investment until it becomes the requirement without any options.
13:15	Recession doesn't affect the technology investment but it might have affected now as people will decide to invest less.

14:10	In Jumeirah there is no problem regarding the understanding the IT benefit in organizational level.
14:50	The main in-room technology will be up-to-date TV and Wi-Fi. An ideal technology can be IP phones. IP phones can create competitive advantage. Making rooms too technical doesn't mean people will use them.
15:25	When room refurbishments took place same time technology will be changed in rooms. Another type of technology that is preferred is the energy saving technologies. Luxury hotels can be seen as an innovative and follow up-to-date technology closer.
16:25	Energy saving perspective does not seen as a preferred option but Hotel Manager considers this option as well. However, having green policy can affect the use of energy saving technology.
18:45	The softwares used are Peak (concierge) and Hotsos (guest request software). Technology is the big part of the everyday life.
18:55	Technology use is getting stabilised as most piece of technology is already implemented in hotels.
19:25	In-room technology doesn't affect the hotel efficiency as it takes a wild to be used by guests or in most of the cases they are not interested.
20:20	As long as the room technology is user friendly, comfortable and entertainment wise there is need to use technology for competitive advantage.

Mr. Elliot Corbett, IT manager and Mr. Jawad Sabir, IT assistant at Jumeirah Carlton Tower

28/02/10 11:00 18:15 minutes

00:40	The main priority of technology implementation will be related to the hotel requirement, competitor's technology use and the current technology performance. (JS) Hospitality technology doesn't have much variety to choose from. So as there is not much choice hotels prefer to stick with the same technology. Financial constraint is the main reason not spent. As the hotel is human-related service operation the less technology is required. Can be seen as a cost hassle rather than a necessity. (E)
02:10	As the chain hotel the decision is made in Head office rather than by individual hotel level. So decision is most of the time governed and made not by the IT manager of the hotel but by Head Office.
02:50	IT related decisions are made by IT director rather than Finance Director as there is CIO in Head Office. As the chain hotel is concerned the all hotels are kept in same level when the budget allocated.
03:15	But as the budget decision is made the finance director will have higher authority level than IT director. But in hotel level GM makes final decision.
05:10	The investment in new technology doesn't create any competitive advantage but it benefits by enhancing the system and integrating different systems. Operationally technology enhances the hotel's efficiency.
06:05	Fast internet can be seen as a competitive advantage. But the

	implementation of the new PMS will not be noticed by the guest so that's it doesn't create direct competitive advantage.
07:20	Training of the staff was the greatest challenge faced during the technology transfer. Jumeirah trainers and Micros trainers were available to give professional training to all staff.
07:40	As the hotel staff work in different shifts it was hard to organize the training process. However, after 5 months of using OPERA hotel staffs feel more confident.
08:00	As it was a new system for everybody the actual technical side went quite smoothly. The training took place before the implementation but staff still in adaptation period.
08:50	Operation wise it is same but the way it is used is different with the new technology you have to keep security up-to-date.
09:15	The training before implementation can be seen as a waste of time as people will forget what they learnt. Having on-the-job training is more effective than the training before the use as they don't face all eventualities in training environment.
10:00	Training before and after implementation can have more effect than only training before implementation. So overlapping training can be recommended.
10:40	As all staff was in learning curve there was no in-house trainer available.
11:10	The training was different from department to department according to the use.
11:50	Only PMS system is changed and all other systems remained the same as they are all integrated to each other and complement with each other.
12:20	When the system is purchased the compatibility of different technologies is tested. As Opera is very widely used it is compatible with the other interfaces.
12:55	Before implementation the system was tested in Head Office. As it is global software it is more reliable and tested everywhere in the world.
13:40	Interfaces were tested before implementation but actual software was tested already.
14:00	Operation wise all technologies have advantages and disadvantages. But technologically it is more advanced and performs better but it is not proven.
14:30	The main advantage of the new technology is related to the database that is run on the Oracle that guarantees that the data will not be lost.
15:00	Changing PMS from Novell operating system to Windows decreased time spent for back-up of the system.
15:50	However, during migration there can be incidents of data losing. But in Jumeirah case they had no such an incident.
15:55	The new system is more efficient in a way that it allows users to use the system constantly even during the back-up so no service is interrupted during the back-up process.
17:00	The main expectations from the new technology was related to the more automated work such as reducing paper work, reducing manual work, and making the information available by integrating different softwares. Centralising information for the all group.
17:20	Better reporting and up-to-date information.

Mr. Guilherme Mayhoffer, Front Office attendant of Jumeirah Carlton Tower. 29/02/2010. 16.00 pm.

0:11:34

01:15	The systems are not compatible with a new PMS which is Opera. As the systems are not compatible it creates problem for staff to use it efficiently. As a result it creates difficulty to use all efficient features of Opera. The current IT infrastructure is not enough for Opera use as Opera require better technology to be faster as the infrastructure is not enough it slows the system down.
02:50	The training provided from Head Office was considered as not enough which affect the use of a new system. As the trainers were provided from head office when the trainers left there was no one who could understand the problems they are facing. Maybe giving for flexibility to the brand hotels to get assistance from outside would be useful.
04:50	Not enough training was provided to some department which resulted into switching to manual works instead of using the better features of a new technology. So instead of eliminating paper works and bring it to paperless work environment they switched to the basics because lack of knowledge.
06:30	Just providing a proper training is not enough. The current computer system is not supporting the use of Opera efficient way as it slows it down.
07:30	Even a new system is better than the previously used FIDELIO system it is not beneficial to use it with no proper training and with no supporting infrastructure.
08:25	It could be more efficient if there were designated trainers were in charge of each department for longer time period.
10:25	The other problem that can be faced is a lost customer profile during the transfer of data from one system to another. As a result most of the regular guests are complaining about it.
10:40	As the system was not set properly it difficult to reach some features even the user is properly trained. As hospitality business deals with the people the unhandled problems will result in losing more customers.

Private	
Private Floor	
Guest	
Reservations	
Guest Services	
Bar	
Restaurant	
Turkey	
United Arab Emirates	
Uruguay	
Russia	
Vietnam	
Venezuela	
Zambia	
South Africa	

11.5 Appendix 5 - List of countries covered

<i>Developing countries</i>	<i>Newly industrialized countries</i>	<i>Industrialized countries</i>
Argentina	Hong Kong	Australia
Bahrain	South Korea	Austria
Bangladesh	Singapore	Belgium
Bolivia	Taiwan	Canada
Brazil	Total 4	Denmark
Bulgaria		Finland
Chile		France
China		Iceland
Colombia		Ireland
Cuba		Italy
Cyprus		Japan
Ecuador		Luxembourg
Egypt		Netherlands
Gibraltar		New Zealand
Grcecc		Norway
Hungary		Spain
India		Sweden
Indonesia		Switzerland
Iran		U.K.
Iraq		U.S.A.
Israel		Germany
Jordan		Total 21
Kenya		
Kuwait		
Macau		
Malaysia		
Mexico		
Oman		
Paraguay		
Peru		
Philippines		
Portugal		
Poland		
Puerto Rico		
Qatar		
Romania		
Saudi Arabia		
Syria		
Thailand		
Turkey		
United Arab Emirates		
Uruguay		
Russia		
Venezuela		
Yugoslavia		
Zambia		
Total 46		